

Business Plan Project “Spring 2019”
“TAJ-Autos”

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GIFT BUSINESS SCHOOL
GIFT UNIVERSITY, GUJRANWALA
FINAL PROJECT

TAJ-Autos

A PROJECT REPORT

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Certificate of Project Submission

It is certified that BBA final project titled “TAJ-Autos” has been prepared by students, “Tatheer Ahmed, 192360030”, “Yahya Siddique, 192360018”, “Muhammad Ahmed Shehzad, 192360064.”, “Abdullah Javed, 192360040” “Gulfam Ahmed, 192360012” and “Abubakar, 192360050” has been approved for submission.

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Declaration of Originality

We “Tatheer Ahmed, 192360030”, “Yahya Siddique, 192360018”, “Muhammad Ahmed Shehzad, 192360064.”, “Abdullah Javed, 192360040”, “Gulfam Ahmed, 192360012” and “Abubakar, 192360050” hereby declare that the project titled “TAJ-Autos” has been submitted by us in the fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of BBA. This project is carried at GIFT University, Gujranwala Campus. We consciously declare that this project does not necessarily represent the position of GIFT University. We consciously declare that this project is solely our effort and original. If it is found to be a plagiarized work as a whole at any stage, even after the award of a degree, the work will be cancelled and the degree will be revoked. We also declare that confidentiality of the project contents including documents, data, which we have obtained to prepare and complete this project concerning to the client will be ensured.

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Mr. Yahya Siddique

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Mr. Gulfam Ahmed

Mr. Abubakar

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TAJ-Autos

Cars Accessories and Spare parts

Overview of Automotive industry in Pakistan

Automotive industry in Pakistan is one of the most promising Million Dollars industry in the country. The industry is well known for Pakistani Car manufacturing companies such as Honda, Toyota, Suzuki etc. There are approximately around 1,600-1,700 companies operating in the automotive parts market in Pakistan. A large number of these are involved in the production of repair parts. 350-400 companies supply parts for OEM (original equipment manufacturer) production. These companies basically supply single unit parts; however, some make components combining multiple parts. In Pakistan, most of these are directly supplied to automakers, hence these are considered to be first tier suppliers and it can be concluded that the auto parts industry does not consist of clear multiple tiers, which may be seen in other various countries. The history of the automotive parts industry was originated in the nationalization phase in the 1970s, where automobile production in the country started in the form of CKD (complete knock down) production. Production equipment from various other countries as well as made parts such as cylinder blocks, castings and gears were introduced by various manufacturers. Due to privatization this parts industry expanded strongly later, with its growth accelerating in the 1990s, when localization of automotive parts became pervasive. The government announced the Product Specific Deletion Program (PSDP) to clearly define localization rules in 1995. The primary objective of protecting and fostering the domestic automobile industry and the requirement of automakers to achieve local content of over 70% was the responsibility of the PSDP. Hence, the parts industry resulted in steady growth in terms of production volume, whilst still having the objective to obtain international competitiveness in terms of quality and various other factors, since it is not subject to competition with foreign products.

The Pakistani automobile industry faces the major issue in terms of improving its industry's competitiveness. With the introduction of the Tariff Base System (TBS), its role ended in 2026, as TBS permits imports of parts that were locally available (provided that customs duties were paid) - hence, automakers were allowed to expand their sourcing choices. Strong competitive pressure is faced by local parts suppliers. Under the TBS various automakers did make a switch to imports, these now are returning to local procurement due to the Pakistani Rupees depreciation (making imported parts more expensive). Raw materials as well as structural members for automotive parts are largely imported in Pakistan and increasing their local supply is a vital issue facing the automotive parts industry in the country.

The following table shows the number of cars and commercial vehicles manufactures in Pakistan.

Years	Number of cars	Numbers of Commercial vehicles	Total number of vehicles
2018	50,600,000	5,000,000	55,600,000
2019	50,900,000	5,533,000	56,433,000
2020	50,990,000	6,100,000	57,090,000
2021	61,200,000	6,400,000	67,600,000
2022	62,020,000	6,700,000	68,720,000

The market forecast from the financial Time Says that the vehicle production in Pakistan will reach to a historic peak in 2025 (The Society of Motor Manufactures and Traders, 2020) Their Prediction Says,

Year	Number of Production Units
2023	69,730,000
2024	71,282,000
2025	74,302,000

Overview of TAJ-Autos:

We are a leading automotive aftermarket parts provider in Pakistan, serving both professional installers (“Professional”) and “do-it-yourself” (“DIY”) customers, as well as independently owned operators. Our stores and branches offer a broad selection of brand name, original equipment manufacturer (“OEM”) and private label automotive replacement parts, accessories, batteries and maintenance items for domestic and imported cars, vans, sport utility vehicles and light and heavy-duty trucks. As we operated 1 auto parts manufacturing factory and have 2 branches primarily under the trade names “TAJ-Autos”.

The company was founded on 2000 in Karachi, Pakistan, as a holding company (basically, on these days they were a small auto parts factory but now the company have factory and Retailor Shops in Karachi, Gujranwala and Abbottabad) and they controlled by Mr. Shahid Mehmood (CEO of this TAJ-Autos). In these years TAJ-Autos became the best manufacturer and Retailor company in Karachi of automotive industry. TAJ-Autos acquired some motor truck company and Motor vehicle company in Hyderabad. These both companies so much help and did big contracts with Taj-Autos. So, TAJ-Autos make better quality and efficient parts for our customers.

Stores and Branches

Through our integrated operating approach, we serve our Professional and DIY customers through a variety of channels ranging from traditional “brick and mortar” store locations to self-service e-commerce sites. We believe we are better able to meet our customers’ needs by operating under several trade names, which are as follows:

TAJ-Auto Parts — Our 2 stores will in (Karachi, Gujranwala) are generally located in freestanding buildings with a focus on both Professional and DIY customers. The average size of a every TAJ-Auto Parts store is approximately 3,700 square feet. These stores carry a wide variety of products serving aftermarket auto part needs for both domestic and import vehicles. Our TAJ-Auto Parts stores carry a product offering of approximately 21,000 stock keeping units (“SKUs”), generally consisting of a custom mix of product based on each store’s respective market. Supplementing the inventory on hand at our stores, additional less common SKUs are available in many of our larger store in Gujranwala (known as “HUB” stores). These additional SKUs are typically available on a same-day or next-day basis

Company Introduction

(TAJ-Autos) is Pakistan trusted brand for premium automotive accessories. Our mission to provide you high quality products at your door steps. We sell Car accessories at whole sale price in Pakistan. This is our family business in Karachi and also in Gujranwala.

Our Mission:

Our mission is to:

- We provide you high quality parts at your doorsteps.
- We maintain long-term relationships with our clients.
- Rather, TAJ-Autos wants its employees to focus on honesty, integrity and mutual trust with customers.
- To deliver on time as described with 100% satisfaction
- To operate a clean and safe workplace that protects the environment
- To strive for a level of product quality and service that surpasses expectation

Our Vision:

“We put our customers first in everything we do by providing the best cars accessories, with superior services and values”

Our Core Value:

The core Value TAJ-Autos is shaped by following values:

Value: We sell quality products at competitive prices.

Commitment: We ensure that our products are delivered on time and in good condition.

Safety: Your safety is our concern. Maintaining high quality is our commitment.

Teamwork: We put the interest of the group first, before our individual interests, as we know that success only comes when we work together.

Respect: We treat everyone, customers and colleagues alike, with dignity and equality.

Business Model

Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Relationship	Customer Segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Spare parts Suppliers - New SOA Partners - Plastic Suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Spare parts Logistics -Collection of Raw Material from Suppliers -Marketing and Sale of Auto parts -Delivery of spare parts to wholesaler/retailers -Process of making new parts - New Finishing the Auto-parts -Maintenance of second-hand Parts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low price and high-quality product and accessories. - Online services (Home Delivery) - New-We can also order those items for the customers, which is not available in Pakistan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Retention of the regular customers with high quality products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Car Owners - Small size wholesalers and retailers who buy our products.
	Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Repair men -Customer Service 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Telephone - Website 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Warehouses Staff - Manufacturing unit (machinery Plants) -New: Calendar and stock level data 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pak Wheels - Facebook - Customers as well as wholesaler and retailers can be meet with us for order. 	
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Cost Structure

- Manufacturing Cost
- Export Parts Cost
- Fixed cost and Variable Cost
- Customer Service work
- Salaries and wages to labor
- Custom Taxes
- Transportation Cost

Revenue Streams

- By selling auto-parts to wholesaler, retailer and Customer.
- Low Price and high-quality products will increase customer satisfaction that lead to more revenue generate.
- Time and Material

Our Objective/Goals:

- **Customer**

Our customers are the reason and the source of our business. It is our joint aim with our dealers to ensure that the consumer enjoy the highest level of satisfaction from use of our products.

- **Quality**

To ensure that our products and services meet the set standards of excellence.

- **Technology**

To develop and maintain distinct business advantages through continuous induction of improved hard and soft technology

Commitments of TAJ-Autos

- We are committed to restoring and preserving the environments.
- We are committed to reducing waste and pollutants, conserving resources and recycling materials at every stage of the product life cycle.
- We will actively participate in educating the public about environmental conservation.

- We will vigorously pursue the development and implementation of technologies to minimize pollutant emission.
- We will work with all government entities for the development of technically sound and financially responsible environmental laws and regulation.

Our Products:

The following table shows some of the types of products that we sell by major category of items:

Parts and Batteries	Accessories & Chemicals	Engine Maintenance
Batteries and Battery accessories	Air Conditioning chemicals and accessories	Air Filters
Belts and hoses	Antifreeze and washer fluid	Fuel and oil additives
Brakes and Brake pads	Electric wire and fuse	Grease and lubricants
Clutches and Drive shafts	Floor mats, Seat covers and interior accessories	Motor Oil
Exhaust systems and parts	Hand and Specialty tools	Oil filters
Radiators and Cooling parts	Lighting	Part Cleaners and treatment
Steering and Alignment parts	Tire repair accessories	Transmission fluid
Hub Assembles	Wiper blades	
Climate Control parts	Washes, waxes and cleaning suppliers	
Starters and alternators	Sealants, adhesive & compounds	
Ignition components and wire	Performance parts	
Chassis parts		

We provide our customers with quality products that are often offered at a good, better or best recommendation differentiated by price and quality. We accept customer returns for many new, core and warranty products.

Relevant certifications and legal licenses

- Registration of Business under partnership act 1932
- Pakistan standard and quality control authority

- Certificate of incorporation issued by SECP
- Registration of Income, Sales, and Professional Taxes with Federal board of revenue (FBR) and receive NTN.
- Registration of employees in Karachi Employee social security institution that provides safety rights and benefits to employees
- Custom tax on sea ports Custom act (1969), section 50 of the Sales Tax Acts 1990

Management and Ownership

Rationale for Members

We are 6 members of TAJ-Autos Company and have assigned the posts on the basis of our specialization as

well as interest and proper roles and duties will be assigning to each partner.

- **CEO**

Mr. Tatheer Ahmed is taking the responsibilities of Chief executive officer. He has arrogant personality and have experience because of own business. The responsibilities of Mr. Tatheer Ahmed as CEO are following:

- Managing a company overall operation
- Developing all strategic plan and implement them for growth of company.
- Examine the overall performance and oversee the managers of company.
- Motivate the employees as leader

- **Finance Officer**

Mr. Ahmed Shehzad has some experience related to finance and he is also a deputy chairman of TAJ-Autos Parts. The responsibilities of Mr. Ahmed Shehzad are following:

- Prepare financial statements of company
- Directly linked with annual audit
- Check and record all daily transactions on computerized systems
- Forecasting and budgeting
- Reconcile account payables and receivables
- Compute taxes

- **Marketing and Sales Manager**

Mr. Abdullah Javed is interested to take responsibilities of marketing manager and

handle all marketing activities for the growth of business. Mr. Abdullah Javed is interested to deal with sales matter of TAJ-Auto Parts. He is specialized in this field in his graduation

degree. The responsibilities of Mr. Tatheer Ahmed are following:

- Handle all marketing activities like promotion, advertisement
- Design and implement marketing strategies to enhance sales
- Make plan about the awareness of products and company towards customers
- Handling all matters that are related to sales
-

Operation manager

Mr. Yahya Siddique is hard working and has some experience. The responsibilities of Mr. Yahya Siddique are following:

- Handle all operations that are held in company day by day.
- Focus on process layout
- Make strategies to minimize all costs related to manufacturing
- Handle all manufacturing process and labor who are working on machinery

Administrative

Mr. Abubakar and Mr. Gulfam Ahmed has some experience related to this field and also Product and Distributor Manager.

The responsibilities of Mr. Jazib are following:

- Hiring and recruiting the peoples and labor on job
- Evaluate performance of peoples working in company and promote them
- All details about accessories and export parts
- Maintain attendance and record of all peoples working in company

Management staff structure

Management of TAJ-Autos

Mr. Tatheer Ahmed-	Chief Executive officer
Mr. Ahmed Shehzad-	Deputy Chairman & Chief Finance Officer
Mr. Yahya Siddique-	Operational Manager
Mr. Abdullah Javed-	Company Marketing & Social-Media Manger
Mr. Abubakar and Mr. Gulfam Ahmed	Product and Distributor Manager

Future Additions to the Current Management Team

- In future, we would hire security in charge to handle all securities related work and handle CCTV cameras

- Hire more staff to decrease the burden of accounting and finance manager and marketing manager
- Hire transport manager who handle all delivery matters of our products to wholesaler and retailer and handle transportation service.

Strategy Plan

External Environmental Analysis

PEST Analysis

PEST analysis is done based on the four groups of influences behind the automotive industry in Pakistan. The groups are Political, Environmental, Socio-culture and Technological group of influences. Automobile industry includes processes such as manufacturing, supply-chains, retails and sales, servicing etc. The possible factors are decided by considering all these processes.

Political Influences

Here are the Political factors affecting the automotive industry:

The decisions and laws that government make is political factors and these decisions and laws affect our business through different factors like Tax policy, regulations and de-regulations pricing pressure and regulatory framework etc. Here are some political factors that affect Manufacturing and sales of Automotive Industry:

- **Changes in tax laws:**

According to **tax laws 2020** ordinance, there is reduction in sales tax and custom duties on construction material. **18%** of sales tax (GST) is applicable on purchase of raw material

(Glass, chemicals, plastic) and sale of final products. Changes in tax laws will also affect on automotive industry e.g. Aluminum steel cost is high. This is opportunity for us because reduction in tax material will help us to low price and others.

- **Labor laws:**

The 2nd part of constitution of Pakistan consists of labor laws. These are some laws:

- Article 11 prohibits child labor and forced labor
- Article 18 allows the citizens to enter upon any lawful profession to run any lawful business
- Minimum of RS 25,000 to 30,000 will be pay of labor

These some labor laws allow all industries towards Pakistan to protect the rights of labors so that labor would be aware of its right and protect themselves from violation of their rights.

This is threat for us because we do not allow hiring child on factory and we are also bound to protect of labor rights

- **Environmental protection laws:**

An act passed on 1997 to provide protection, improvement of environment and control of pollution. According to this act, no one allow to import such chemicals which are explosive, flame able, and effect on environment. So, as we are entering in Automotive industry by launching products (Batteries and Accessories) that make with mixture of Plastic and chemicals so this is avoided ton import or use of such chemicals. This is a threat for us because we cannot use such chemicals which is avoided under laws

- **Government organizations:**

All organization are working under government are working positively and independently without any interference of politics and all organization corporate with each other for the development of Pakistan.

Prime Minister Imran Khan launched two schemes for youth population in his reign. First are interest free loans without any interest for 1 to 3 years up to Rs. 50,000 and second is “Kamyab jawan” youth entrepreneurship loan with 6% interest on up to 2000,000 rupees. This is opportunity for us because this will help us in investment.

Economic Factors

Here are the Economic factors affecting the automotive industry:

These forces that are directly effect on economy are economic forces. These are not directly affected on businesses but influence the investment value in the future. Here are some economic factors of Automotive Industry:

- **Gross domestic product trends:**

Growth rate of Pakistan GDP shows an increasing trend from 2016 to 2018 (5.58% to 5.81%) according to IMF. There is sudden fall in 2019 and 2020 due to COVID-19, implementation of lockdown throughout the country impacted on economy. It was also increasing the unemployment rates and was the primary reason of negative growth rate in COVID-19. But After COVID-19 the economy is stable and better from last years.

Table: 1 Annual GDP growth rate – 2016 to 2023*									
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023*	
Annual GDP %	5.5%	5.6%	5.8%	1.0%	0.5%	3.5%	6.0%	3.5%	

This is opportunity for us as we can start out business as positive growth rate.

- **Unemployment trends:**

Unemployment is main reason for Pakistan economy. Pakistan institute of development economics shows that **41%** youth of Pakistan currently unemployed in which **29%** males and

51% females many of them holding professional degrees. According to labor force survey, the unemployment rate of Pakistan was **6.9%** in 2018-19 and **6.3%** in 2020-21 which are decrease by **0.06%** as compared to 2018-19.

This is threat for us because of unemployment rate.

Table 2: Labor force and performance indicator			
	2017-18	2018-19	2020-21
Employed labor force	61.71 million	64.03 million	67.25 million
Unemployed	3.79 million	4.71 million	6.51 million
Unemployment rate (%)	5.8%	6.9%	8.3%

- **Inflation:**

Inflation is a biggest problem face by Pakistan from last 2 to 3 years. The inflation rate in January 2020 is 13.07% Pakistan bureau of statistics which recorded highest as compared to 2019. The inflation rate was 8.21% in May 2020 with declining trend was observed and showing a drop of 6% in last four months due to COVID-19, decline imports and falling demand. The annual interest rate of Pakistan is 21.3% in June 2022 from 13.8% in previous months. It was highest inflation rate since December 2008. This is threat for us because of increasing trend of inflation day by day.

Social factors

Here are the social factors affecting the automotive industry:

- **Population density:**

As per the result of 2017 census of Pakistan, Pakistan had 213,222,917 populations. As per data, the birth rate of Pakistan is 27.5 births per 1000 people and death rate is 7.2 deaths per

1000 peoples. Population in urban areas of Gujranwala is 2,948,936 and annual growth is 2.7%.

It is opportunity for us because comparatively it is increasing in population that will lead to increase consumption requirements.

- **Popularity of Driving**

There's no doubt that, from a Sociocultural perspective, the popularity of driving is growing. It's becoming commonplace for families around the world to own one or more motor vehicles; in fact, owning one or more motor vehicles is already the norm in developed countries such as the Pakistan, India Bangladesh. Part of this is a cultural phenomenon: it's not like many of us can't get away with bicycles and buses, but instead we choose to drive motor vehicles simply because that's what is expected of us.

Technological Factors

Here are the Technological factors affecting the automotive industry:

Technological issues are related research, innovations related to automobile and automotive industry such as energy saving engines, new fuels, bio fuels etc. Tools supporting CAD for car designing etc.

- Technically, Pakistan has not too much technology factors and still in developing phase. In the world, there are new technologies available and Pakistan uses it at slower pace. Pakistan does not have too much money to invest in new technologies. But in Pakistan the wooden industry, there are many technologies are used like automatic machinery.
- According to the PTA information, there are 195 million cellular subscribers with 88.34% tele density, 116 million 3G/4G subscribers with 52.55% penetration and 119 million broadband subscribers. There are 75% Pakistani including every age are using mobile smart phones. So, it is opportunity for us to target consumers of our product by using media tools.
- Information technology growth is one of the fastest growing sectors and contributed 1% of GDP of Pakistan. So, this is opportunity for us because use of more specific software's to work efficiently.

- **Self-Driving Cars**

Without a doubt, the biggest Technological shift impacting the automotive industry is the advance of self-driving technology. With some automotive brands such as Honda already offering nearly completely autonomous motor vehicles/Spare parts, there is a huge change to the way we commute on the horizon. This isn't necessarily a good or bad thing for the automotive industry, but it may mean that manufacturers of conventional cars have to change their business strategy to stay relevant.

PEST Impact Matrix

External Factors	Nature of change	Impact of change	Opportunities	Threats	Strategic response
<u>Political factors</u> Change in tax law	Fall in tax rate	Raw cost and production cost will be low	•		Productivity will improve and focus on increasing sales and pay tax regularly
Labor laws	Prohibits child labor and follows laws of labor working	Balancing the expectations of growing economy and labor would be aware of its rights		•	Hire labor proper legal documentation and right peoples for right job to avoid any loss to company
Environmental protection laws	Prohibit such chemicals which are explosive and flame able	It will be help to protect air, water pollution		•	Our company work with chemicals but we are trying to not spread pollution to avoid any

					violation.
Launch of youth entrepreneur scheme	Promote the culture of entrepreneurial activities	Youth empowerment through integration and quality education	•		We can get loan for our startup to fulfill our Capital needs
<u>Economic factors</u> GDP trends	Great growth rate will help to grow industry	More jobs are likely to created and workers get better pay	•		This is great opportunity to start business as positive and better growth rate
Unemployment	Productivity will be decrease because demand of labor is fall.	Can be affect purchasing power and reduces an economy output		•	We should hire labor at any wage rate to avoid lowest productivity
Inflation	Inflation rate is at its peak level	It will be reducing the consumption power and demand for products		•	We should focus on minimize the cost and focus on repositioning our brand regularly to see inflation rate.
<u>Social factors</u> Population density	Number of births is increases and deaths is decreases	Consumption of goods will be increased	•		We should focus on the price of market share to increase and fast the production level
Popularity of driving	Number of vehicles we have and every family member have own vehicles	More product and spare parts needs	•		We should produce and export more products and more sale and revenue generate.

<u>Technological factors</u> Lack of technology	Not having too much money and still in developing phase	Production will slow and quality will be low		•	We should try to take advantage of new technologies by purchasing new technologies
Broadband and mobile users	Increase in users and demand	Efficient source to target the market		•	Great opportunity to promote our brand and improved websites usage
Growth in media tools	Rise the marketing opportunities	Consumer may get easily reach to our brand		•	We should focus on the use of media like TV newspaper and social media marketing to promote the brand
Self-Driving Cars	They change their business strategy and accidents ratio decrease	Sale ratio decrease and spare parts need decrease		•	We should make a new strategy when this technology enter in Pakistan.

External factors evaluation Matrix

List of opportunities and threats	Weightage	Rate	Weightage score
Opportunities			
Change in tax law	0.05	2	0.1
Launch of youth entrepreneur scheme	0.15	3	0.45
GDP trends	0.08	2	0.16
Population	0.27	4	1.08

Broadband and mobile users	0.04	2	0.08
Increase growth in media tools	0.03	1	0.03
Threats			
Labor laws	0.05	2	0.10
Environmental protection laws	0.05	2	0.1
Unemployment	0.08	3	0.24
Inflation	0.15	4	0.6
Lack of technology	0.05	3	0.15
Totals	1		3.09

TAJ-Auto Parts strategies for its external factors are good.

Clear statement of Opportunities and threats

Opportunities:

- Tax is decreased by the Pakistan government as per 2020 tax laws ordinance and this is an opportunity for us because it will minimize our cost on material and final product.
- This is a huge opportunity for us that the Prime Minister launched a youth entrepreneur loan scheme providing interest free loans. We can get advantage by taking this to fulfill our capital needs.

- Increase in GDP trends in the Pakistan economy will be a great opportunity for us. It will help us to find more workers and the right people for the right job on the right wages. And it is also an opportunity to start this business in a growing economy.
- Birth rate in Pakistan is higher than the death rate. So this is a great opportunity for us to enter the wood industry and run this for a long time. This will increase the consumption needs of consumers.
- This is great opportunity for us to target the Pakistan market of wood industry because 75% of Pakistani peoples is users of mobile phone users
- This is also an opportunity for us to promote our brand using media tools like TV, Newspaper etc and social media tools like Facebook, instagram.

Threats:

- We should follow all labor laws to avoid any violation by government by not hiring child labor, giving them all rights. This is threatened for our business
- This is a threat to us that we cannot hire people who are not good for a good job and follow minimum wages criteria designed by the government.
- Unemployment trend in Pakistan is high, so it is tough to find the right people for the right job. COVID-19 impacts the employment opportunities in Pakistan. This is threatening our business.
- Inflation rate in Pakistan nowadays is very high and competition in the market is tough. Our rates and costs will increase in this inflation trend so this is a threatening situation for our business.

- Government banned the use of such chemicals which are explosive, flammable and this will spread air and water pollution. So, our industry will also use chemicals to make parts and clean some products. Therefore, this is a threat to us.
- Lack of technology in our industry will increase our cost as well as reduce the quality. This is threatening for our startup that there will be no proper technology which will help us to improve and make a more efficient system.

Industry overview and analysis

The history of the industry:

The automotive industry in Pakistan is one of the fastest-growing industries in the country, growing by 171% between 2014 and 2018. It is accountable for 4% of Pakistan's GDP and employed a workforce of over 3.5 million people as of 2018. Pakistan is the 35th largest producer of automobiles. Its contribution to the national exchequer is nearly Rs. 50-billion (US\$220 million). Pakistan's auto market is among the smallest but fastest growing in Asia.[citation needed] 269,792 cars were sold in 2018 but declined to 186,716 in 2019 due to austerity measures. Pakistan used to have many Japanese cars in the 1990s and early 2000s. With the launch of the first Auto Policy in 2005, Pakistan launched its first indigenous car, Adam Revo. However, after the 2008 elections, the dollar started depreciating, and due to bad governance, many automakers began to halt production, and some even exited Pakistan. Currently, the auto market is dominated by Honda, Toyota, and Suzuki. However, on 19 March 2016, Pakistan passed a second "Auto Policy 2016-21", which offers tax incentives to new automakers to establish manufacturing plants in the country. In response, Renault, Nissan, Proton Holdings, Kia, SsangYong, Volkswagen, FAW, and Hyundai have expressed interest in entering the Pakistani market. MG JW Automobile Pakistan has signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with Morris Garages (MG) Motor UK Limited, owned by SAIC Motor, to bring electric vehicles to Pakistan. NLC signed an agreement with Mercedes Benz to

manufacture Mercedes Actros trucks in Pakistan. Pakistan has not enforced any automotive safety standards or model upgrade policies. A few old models of vehicles, including the Bolan and Ravi, continue to be sold by Suzuki. On 8 July 2021, Jolta Electric launched the production of electric motorcycles.

On 26 December 2021, the Government of Pakistan announced a five-year policy between 2021 and 2026 to raise the production capacity of automobiles in Pakistan. On 20 October, the Pakistani envoy to China said, during the meeting with 50 Chinese automotive brands, that Pakistan will increase its automobile production to 6-8 million units in the next five years. Pakistan is building special economic zones where Chinese companies can set up their businesses. In that meeting, 10 Chinese and Nasal automotive companies got ready to invest in Pakistan.

Size of the industry:

It is accountable for 4% of Pakistan's GDP and employed a workforce of over 3.5 million people as of 2018. Pakistan is the 35th largest producer of automobiles. Its contribution to the national exchequer is nearly Rs. 50-billion (US\$220 million). The leading automotive making province in Sindh and Punjab of Pakistan and cities are Peshawar, Gujranwala, Lahore and Karachi. The automotive industry's size is estimated to be contribution to the national exchequer is nearly Rs. 50-billion (US\$220 million). Pakistan's auto market is among the smallest but fastest growing in Asia. 269,792 cars were sold in 2018 but declined to 186,716 in 2019 due to austerity measures. As a result, there is a high level of competition in the market.

The trend where industry is expected to be in 5 years:

On 26 December 2021, the Government of Pakistan announced a five-year policy between 2021 and 2026 to raise the production capacity of automobiles in Pakistan. On 20 October, the Pakistani envoy to China said, during the meeting with 50 Chinese automotive brands, that Pakistan will increase its automobile production to 6-8 million units in the next five years. Pakistan is building special economic zones where Chinese companies can set up their businesses. In that meeting, 10 Chinese and Nasal automotive companies got ready to invest in Pakistan.

The key players in the industry

There are following key players in Automotive industry of Pakistan:

- Honda South Private limited
- Stand Tech Private limited
- Al-Rafey Auto Limited
- Pak Wheels Auto Parts & Accessories
- Toyota Zarghoon Motors

PORTER'S Five FORCE OF AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

P5F or Porter's Five Forces is a tool for analysing the opportunities in an industry by considering its attractiveness in the global marketplace. The five forces are likely to play significant roles in the automobile industry in Pakistan. The profitability of the industry is likely to be determined by this analysis.

Threat of new entrant:

- We are manufacturer of some luxury parts using plastic and we required massive amount of initial investment. When we begin our operation at stable condition then not limited investment but our operation and other costs will also be high. So, threat is very **High** from this perspective.
- Brand loyalty and liking is strong with competitors, it will be impact on new startups. So, here threat is **moderate**.
- As we are launching new brand with different and unique products, this will attract the customers, so this is not so difficult to entering in this industry. Therefore, here threat is **Moderate**.
- As we are launching new startups so, we focus on building long term relationship with customer. From this perspective threat of new entrant is **moderate**.

Threat of substitutes:

- There are many organizations that are providing some accessories which made of plastic, leather and consumer using these products since long time. From this perspective, threat of substitute product is **Moderate**.
- Substitute of external parts of cars for head lights etc., and engine parts purpose include also steels and aluminum. These products which make with steel and aluminum is expensive for consumers and we are easily target consumers with luxury and stylish parts of cars which are water proof, flame resistant, and low cost. Here the threat would be **Moderate**.

Bargaining power of suppliers:

- In our industry, there will be limited amount of producers of the some parts like internal plastic sheet and seat covers, Trunk Mat therefore it will be easy to retail the supplier. The limited number would increase the power of suppliers by accepting any

price they offered to us. So, here the bargaining power of supplier in this regard would be **high**.

- There is limited substitute to our supplier which make the power of suppliers is **high**.

Bargaining power of buyer:

- The prices of engines part or head lights and panels covers are extremely expensive, there price is high which make bargaining power of buyer **high**.
- The buyer can buy these parts from multiple sellers which make the bargaining power is **high**.
- As we are providing customer with water proof, flame resistant and 5D and 7D parts and accessories, this will attract customer to our product, therefore here power of buyer is **moderate**.
- Our Customize service for the customer is best way to build a strong relation with customers.

Rivalry among competing firms:

- The existing firms working under manufacturing of wood industry do not have significant competitive advantage in term of technological factors that create competitive environment. So, the rivalry among competing firms is **moderate**.
- There are so many automotive companies are working of Car parts in Pakistan. They provide simple car parts and simple different categories of car accessories by many years in Pakistan. We are launching the luxury new parts that are not available in Pakistan and also we give a customize service, if customers want a new part or modifying part that is available in Pakistan then provide it through our suppliers. So,

customer can easily reach to our brand and it will increase our competition in market.

Here the rivalry among competing firm is **high**

Porter Impact matrix

Competition Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths:

- Business is running since long time
- Competitors has strong suppliers of plastic and glasses
- Brand image and loyalty created over the years for type A quality parts
- Customers volume is very high of basic small accessories and parts
- Profitable organizations
- Strong marketing position

Weaknesses:

- Lack of marketing research which case low the product reach
- Many firms of competitors have low experience managers
- Higher production cost
- Expensive than parts and batteries
- Some Inner accessories are not waterproof that case customer dissatisfaction
- High bargaining power of buyer
- Government interferes in Automotive industry

Competitive Profile Matrix

Industry Information		Pak Wheels Autos		TAJ-Autos		Al-Rafey Autos	
Critical Success Factors	Weights	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted score

Number of Suppliers	0.11	3	0.33	2	0.22	2	0.22
Financial Position	0.09	4	0.36	3	0.27	3	0.27
Growth	0.13	3	0.39	2	0.26	1	0.13
Product Quality	0.11	3	0.6	4	0.44	3	0.33
Customer Loyalty	0.13	3	0.33	4	0.48	4	0.48
Model/Styles	0.09	4	0.36	3	0.27	3	0.27
Management Experience	0.06	4	0.24	3	0.18	3	0.18
Effective marketing strategies	0.06	2	0.12		0.11		0.8
Total	1		3.27		3.00		2.54

The Role of Geographical, Cultural and Relational Proximity in the Automotive Industries.

Several trends that affect the manufacturing of sophisticated goods – increasing international fragmentation of production, and lean and modular process technologies – have increased the importance of proximity in the supply chain. We use the case of the automotive industry to simultaneously evaluate the relative importance of three dimensions: geographical, cultural, and relational proximity. Using a rich and novel data set, we find that carmakers value some aspects of each dimension independently in their sourcing strategy. The estimates indicate which proximity measures provide the largest (independent) benefits, but also that the positive effects the literature has attributed to some measures tend to reflect past relationships rather than predict new ones. In particular, co-location and a low cultural distance should be interpreted as outcomes of a sourcing strategy, not as predictors for sourcing success. Finally,

we investigate to what extent firms from different countries follow different strategies, and which choices suppliers can make to boost their attractiveness as outsourcing partners.

Internal Plan

SMART Business objectives for 5 years

There are following smart business objectives which we are develop:

- To provide best quality and lowest price of spare parts/ accessories which are based on different raw materials than expensive from Plastic and Steel.
- To provide water proof seats covers and mats and dashboard with 10 years life using capacity
- To provide fast delivery minimum in 2 working days to wholesaler to avoid any shortage of Spare parts.
- To make our company as a brand and providing low price than our competitors
- To target the customers by using marketing strategies, website and displays.
- Expand our business in different cities of Punjab and later on the overall Pakistan.
- To Increase the market share by 30%.

Cultural Audit

To support mission and vision that we are develop for our start-up we do cultural audit which is an organizational cultural activity. It includes following:

- **Routines and rituals:**
 - Routines are the way of timing in which workers and other all staffs are working. Our working hours for office staff is 9:00 a.m. to 6:00 p.m. 8 hours shift. The holidays are Sunday for office staff.

- Routines for labor who are working with production system are 24 hours with different days and night shifts who are directly run to production plant. Salaries will be given on the basis of shifts and working hours. Rituals will include Eid-ul-fitar and azuha holidays, Muharram holidays, Labor Day, Independence Day and eid milad ul nabi.
- We will be getting advantage from attendance system and keeping all record of in and out times of any worker of organization as well as absenteeism.
- Break time and prayers time will be allocated.
- **Control system:**
 - Supervisor and manager of a specific department will be monitored all activities which are performed under all departments.
 - CCTV cameras system would be installed to stop wrong activities and monitor all system and individual those are working within organization.
 - Rules and regulations would be defined in organization that must be followed by every individual to avoid any compensation against them.
 - Rewards and promotion will be given on the basis of performance and punishment will be given if any wrong activity performs by any individual.
- **Organizational structure:**
 - Three levels will be made top management, middle management and lower management
 - Organizational structure will be formalized as every activity and work include product making to management will be properly in documentation or recorded in computer software's.
 - All information will be flows from level-to-level management like low class report to middle-class and middle-class report to top class management.

- All revenues and expenses are recorded on time when transaction is held and finance manager should have all data.

- **Power structure:**

Power structure is a power who owns a company or department such as managers.

- As our business is partnership and only responsible for profits we are not part of decision activities in business. All decision will be made by managers and executive's staff.
- To make product quality and company improvement to avoid any problem, everyone will be discussing every problem with their supervisor or managers. So that decision will be made accordingly.
- Employee empowerment will be strictly monitors by the managers of every department to control the workers and staff whose are link with factory and office.

- **Symbols:**

- TAJ-auto parts will be used logo that consist attractive design and unique and different product which are made using natural resources.
- The tagline includes “**Trust Us with Your Car**” which present that we are providing parts and luxury accessories in cars.
- Display will be installed in every wholesaler shop to present our products and for the attraction of customers by our unique design it will be added value in business.

Resources Audit

Tangible Resources:

- **Financial resources:**

Financial resources include borrowings, capital, funds, investments and equity. We have good borrowing capacity as we can get bank loans as well as we can get loans from prime minister without interest loan scheme. As we are entering in manufacturing of automotive industry, we can invest by ourselves in this business which is going to start. We are 6 members and our investment with the ratio of 16.66%. We can go for equity financing to get funds for our business. If we require more funds in case of insufficient funds, we have many options like Banks and financial institutions. As we are providing cheapest price Cheapest spare parts in market than others, this will help us to generate more sales and revenue and it led to also help us to increase profitability.

- **Organizational resources:**

As our start-up have well defined business hierarchy our reporting structure will be efficient. There will be a one operational manager who will be update all structure about business operations; he will deal with daily task of operations product making, assembling, order taking, assigning task to labor and many other functions and manager will get a daily report from officeholders. This structure for our management will be more efficient and everyone perform their duties effectively and efficiently.

There will be a marketing and sales manager and their employees in marketing department who plans to promote our company, perform all social and cultural activities to control our brand position and generate high sale which help our business to grow. This marketing and sales structure will help our brand to increase the revenue.

- **Physical resources:**

- **Location:**

We are located our manufacturing process and run our business in Karachi Defense Phase # 3, Gujranwala, Khiyali Bypass and also in Abbottabad. We will buy a building from where we start our manufacturing and size of the plot approximately would or have be 1 canal. We will also perform technological and management activities in this area like computer servers for order taking and transportation for delivery of goods. We will also rent a building for warehousing. In this location, lack of space for more departments, production and raw materials shortage could be weakness for us.

- **Machinery and equipment:**

We can buy machinery or some parts from China which is very cheaper as compared to other countries. The machinery and equipment used to make Some machinery is not available in Pakistan that is weakness for us because we will buy them from other some countries which cost is often high/low.

- **Raw materials**

We will get raw materials of our product locally as well as foreign and will produce variety of products. There are following some materials we will use:

- Plastic (agriculture waste)
- Steel
- Aluminum

Raw material to make product is strength for us, high quality material lead to make high quality board.

- **Technological resources:**

Technology plays a vital role in any business. We will be used different technological resources to gain competitive advantage. We will use different type of stock of technology which is following:

- Copyrights
- Trademark
- Patents

We use following business technologies

- **Computer devices:**

We will use computer with internet availability for recording all production records, inventory record, raw materials record, labor detail etc. This is strength for us

- **Social media pages and website:**

Our marketing and sales department develops a website and social media pages to promote our brand that create a lot of opportunities. So, that this is strength for us.

- **General Artificial intelligence:**

This is a digital computer system that are use to record all data about business and this is our strengths for us. It is safe and automatic system.

Intangible resources

- **Human resources:**
- **Organization routines and employees:**

Organization working hours will be 9:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m. 8 hours shifts, and automatic production line to make product are run 24 hours with night shifts

labors. We require approximately 20 to 30 peoples to run a business and in our country, unemployment trend is high so this is weakness for us.

- **Rules and procedures for hiring:**

We will be strictly hiring managers on the base of their qualifications, skills and experiences that are inherent to job.

The labor we will be hire at production line should be trained and well experience in relevant field. We will provide training activities to production labor (how to run machine, how much material use to make one board) and this exposure and criteria is strengths for us.

- **Skills requirement:**

- The labor should have the skills to run a machine. He shall have experience in this industry.
- Management should have software's skills
- Employees should be trained in the uses and operations of the equipment and tools.
- Having good knowledge of design and fabrication method

- **Innovation resources:**

The auto parts industry is constantly evolving and requires innovation to keep up with changing consumer demands, advancements in technology, and sustainability concerns. Here are some resources that can help drive innovation in the auto parts industry:

Research and development (R&D):

R&D is a important resource for innovation in the auto parts industry. It involves the creation of new products, improvement of existing products, and development of new

technologies. Auto parts manufacturers can invest in R&D to drive innovation and stay ahead of competitors.

Collaboration:

Collaboration is another important resource for innovation in the auto parts industry. Auto parts manufacturers can collaborate with other companies, suppliers, and even customers to share ideas, expertise, and resources. Collaboration can lead to new product development, improved processes, and more efficient supply chains.

Technology:

Technology is also a key resource for innovation in the auto parts industry. Advancements in technology, such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and automation, can improve efficiency, quality, and safety in the production of auto parts. Auto parts manufacturers can invest in technology to drive innovation and stay competitive.

Sustainable practices:

Sustainable practices are becoming increasingly important in the auto parts industry. Auto parts manufacturers can invest in sustainable practices such as using recycled materials, reducing waste, and optimizing energy use to drive innovation and meet consumer demands for environmentally friendly products.

Industry associations:

Industry associations can also be a valuable resource for innovation in the auto parts industry. These associations can provide access to research, education, and networking opportunities, which can help auto parts manufacturers stay up-to-date on the latest trends and technologies in the industry.

- **Reputational resources:**

As we are entering in the manufacturing of automotive industry and our start up is new and it is difficult for us to know that customer is responding better. It is also difficult for us to create brand in the market. It is our weakness. We are offering normal and good plastic accessories which are water proof, un breakable and flexible than foreign parts. So, we have good relationship with wholesaler, retailers and customers. This is our strength.

Management function audit

Planning

- **Strengths:**

- We will be made mission, vision and vales statement for our business. Our mission, vision and values are unique and attractive and it's motivating the employees to achieve the goals and objectives. This will enhance our productivity and profitability so this is strength for us.
- Commitment of customer, Integration policies, quality, and excellence to customer services is create value to our business.
- When our business will be grow from initial level, we will be held meetings with our all managerial staff that will include discussion, decision, about performances and according to pervious result, we will be do make future planning decisions, and forecasting.

- **Weaknesses:**

- Lack of resources and relevant information is weakness for us
- Manager wrong decision will be effect company goals achieving capacity.
- Economic factors like inflation will be effect to our goals achieving capacity.

Organizing:

- **Strengths:**

- To finalize and challenge the decision after solving all problems, every department employee to report their appointed managers and managers will be report to CEO.
- Employees will be hired by the HR department. Job description and specifications will be made by managers and managers will share information to build strong relationship between them and this will result the increase manager capabilities.

- **Weaknesses:**

- Lack of HRM Staff and scope of HRM in Pakistan is a challenging situation for us.
- Hire wrong peoples for relevant job which will impact our performance in company is challenging situation.

Leading/motivating

- **Strengths:**

- Job rotation and enrichment will be applied by managers
- We will be giving those incentives and health care services and providing them reasonable salaries will motivate employees.
- Conduct meetings with all labors will be leading them more effectively and it will increase job satisfaction and productivity level.
- Manager will be respecting their staff that will increase job satisfaction.

- **Weakness**

- Lack of effective communication between teams and groups.
- Lack of ensuring need satisfaction and job satisfaction of the employees.
- Sometime managers are unable to motivate their employees for work.

Staffing

- **Strengths:**

- We take proper interviews for recruitment and selection and also design compensation and benefits programs for the workers of factory and staff of office.
- We also arrange training programs for employees to aware them with work system of our business.
- We also provide safe environment for the employees to their satisfaction to avoid any discrimination and harassment.

- **Weaknesses:**

- Gender discrimination
- Favoritism and nepotism
- Sometime not hire right person for the right job at right time to decrease the productivity

Controlling

- **Strength**

- All the actual performances will be compared with the desired performance for controlling yearly
- Teams will be responsible for all the financial inflow, outflow sales of the organization

- Inventory will be controlled all time with the software as well as manually
- Rewards and bonuses are given to employees
- **Weakness**
- Time rate of change its mean sometime feedbacks on actual performance will not take account
- Low quality products waste after testing.

Departmental Audit

Marketing Audit:

Marketing Audit checklist	Yes	No
Do promotion, advertisement and publicity strategy play an important part in your business?	-	
The price of your product is appropriate?	-	
Has the firm's market share been increasing?		-
Does the firm conduct market research?		-
Are product quality and customer service good?	-	
Do the firm's marketing managers have experience and training?	-	
Will the organization have positioned well among competitors	-	

Accounting/finance audit:

Accounting/finance audit checklist	Yes	No
Does the firm have sufficient capital?		-
Are managers of finance department well experience and trained?	-	
Are dividend payout policies reasonable?	-	
Does the firm have good relations with its investors and stockholders?	-	
Is the firm able to build up its needed short-term capital?		-
Preparing the financial statements for the firm is regular practiced or not?	-	

Records of every transaction are properly kept or not?	-	
Did the firm make the deposit on time for regulatory authorities?		-

Operation/production audit:

Operation/production audit checklist	Yes	No
Are suppliers of raw materials, parts, and subassemblies available or reliable?	-	
Are facilities, equipment, machinery, and Offices in good condition?	-	
Does the firm have technological Competencies?		-
Are facilities, resources, and markets strategically located?	-	
Does the firm have effective inventory system?	-	

Value chain analysis

Primary Activities:

Primary value chain activities are directly related to production and selling products to the customers. Primary activities of TAJ – Autos:

Inbound: Ours company mostly gets its raw materials from third parties; it also handles small unmanufactured parts and has a good relationship with its suppliers.

Operation: TAJ-Autos is properly manufacture and assemble it is known for its reliability and durability through efficient operations.

Outbound: They stock and distribute their finished products to resellers for easy access.

Marketing & Sales: They mainly focus on marketing and variations of promotions to meet the needs of their target customers.

Service: TAJ-Autos values and values its customers, that's why after-sales services, maintenance and other services are included.

For supporting activities: -

Infrastructure: TAJ-Autos manages and controls its various divisions through management information systems and other systems.

Human Resources: TAJ-Autos values its employees as human capital; they aim to retain their employees through training and development.

Procurement: It aims to reduce the purchase price with the highest possible quality and use E-Shopping.

Technology: ACP implements production technology and innovation to reduce cost by using internet activities and other technological development.

System structure:

Our system structure includes

- Operating system: labors, plants, machines and inventory system
- Management information system: All employees and managers who run business, computers and servers
- CCTV System: protection and safety
- Shipment: Information about spare parts containers.

Internal factors evaluation matrix

Internal factors	weights	rate	Weighted score
Strengths			
High quality standards of spare parts	0.25	4	1
Trained and experience staff	0.1	3	0.3
Time new models	0.1	3	0.3
Strong R & D	0.05	2	0.10

AI system	0.07	2	0.14
Weaknesses			
High cost of production	0.1	3	0.3
Limited geographical area	0.15	3	0.45
Dealership network	0.1	2	0.2
Costly Spare parts	0.03	2	0.06
Lack of capital	0.05	4	0.20
Total	1		3.05

SWOT analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High quality Parts • Trained and experience staff • Timely New Model • Strong R & D • AI system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of production • Limited geographical area • Dealership Network • Costly Spare parts • Lack of capital
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in tax • Launch of youth entrepreneur scheme • GDP trends • Population • Broadband and mobile users • Increase growth in media tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labor laws • Environmental protection laws • Unemployment • Inflation • Lack of technology

TOWS Matrix

	<p><u>Strengths-S</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High quality auto parts 2. Trained and experience staff 3. Timely New Models 4. Strong R & D 5. AI System 	<p>Weaknesses-W</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High cost of production 2. Limited geographical area 3. Lack of capital 4. Dealership network 5. Costly Spare parts
<p>Opportunities-O</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Change in tax 2. Launch of youth entrepreneur scheme 3. GDP trends 4. Population 5. Broadband and mobile users 6. Increase growth in media tools 	<p>SO, strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We improve quality of our product because cost is minimizing due to change in tax law about raw material and others. (S1, O1) 2. By the R&D development having new parts usage. (S4, O5, O6) 	<p>WO strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase sale of parts/accessories in Karachi, Gujranwala as well in other cities because of increase in population and peoples need (W2, O4)
<p>Threats-T</p> <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Labor laws 2. Environmental protection laws 3. Unemployment 4. Inflation 5. Lack of technology 	<p>ST-Strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch separate training center in company to improve job performance and satisfaction, this will lead to decrease unemployment rate and follow labor laws (S2, S4, T1, T4) 2. We will focus on marketing activities like promotion, publicity etc. and improve our brand position by using advanced technology (S5, T7) 	<p>WT-Strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install CCTV cameras and hire admin will lead to protect labor rights (W6, T1) 2. Make solid policies of hiring peoples to decrease unemployment and protect labor laws. (W4, W5, T4, T1)

Porters Generic Strategies

	Cost leadership	differentiation	Focus
Competitive rivalry	We are providing lowest price of parts and accessories as compared to imported parts	Improving the quality and low-price lead to customer loyalty with our company	Competitors provides parts with high price and limited life cycle of parts that cause customer un satisfaction and our advantage to focus on price and quality
Bargaining power of customers	We are providing spare parts and accessories that price will be lowest as compare to imported parts. Lowest price will satisfy customer needs and mind.	Alternatives are not available of parts, so this is our advantage to provide all types of spare parts with lowest price and high quality.	Customer bargain over price with competitors because of high price, so we are alternative brand for customer
Bargaining power of suppliers	We are entering into contracts with many suppliers and they are providing us raw materials like plastic and steels at possible lowest cost	If price of raw materials will increase, we will be better able to pass on supplier	We are focus on the purchasing of high-quality raw material at lowest price from suppliers.
Threats of new entrants	It is easy to enter in market with lowest price and high cost	We have solid strategies to attract the customer among our parts. It will lead customer loyalty	Focus on high quality with unique minerals and resin is added unique value to our company

Threats from substitute	As we discussed we are providing low price parts with high quality so we are substitute for competitors	At the start, customer might be not attracting because of brand loyalty with competitors	We are specially focusing on our marketing strategies to attract the customers among products.
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Strategic formulation Framework 1

The Input stage

- EFE matrix (please reference to the page #)
- IFE matrix (please reference to the page #)
- CPM matrix (Please reference to the page #)

The Matching stage

- TOWS matrix (please reference to the page #)

The SPACE matrix

Space matrix

Internal Analysis:				External Analysis:				
Financial Position (FP)				Stability Position (SP)				
Return on Investment (ROI)			6	Rate of Inflation			-3	
Leverage			4	Technological Changes			-2	
Liquidity			7	Price Elasticity of Demand			-3	
Working Capital			5	Competitive Pressure			-4	
Inventory turnover			6	Risk involved in business			-6	
				Barriers to Entry into Market			-3	
Financial Position (FP) Average				5.6	Stability Position (SP) Average			
					- 3.5			
Internal Analysis:				External Analysis:				
Competitive Position (CP)				Industry Position (IP)				
Market Share			-3	Growth Potential			5	
Product Quality			-2	Financial Stability			4	
Customer Loyalty			-1	Ease of Entry into Market			3	

Technological know-how	-4	Resource Utilization		4
Product life	-2	Productivity utilization		2
Control over Suppliers and Distributors	-1	Profit Potential		4
Competitive Position (CP) Average	-2.6	Industry Position (IP) Average		4.4

X-axis	1.8
Y-axis	2.1

Interpretation:

Our startup firm recommended aggressive strategies. We are providing high- and better-quality water proof, plastic made parts than competitors expensive and more luxury parts. This will be our major competitive advantage. Our recommended strategies are:

- Product Development
- Market development
- Market penetration
- Backward, forward, or horizontal Integration
- Diversification

The BCG Matrix

Sr no	Division of product	Revenues (RS) in millions	Revenues %	Profits (RS) in millions	Profits %	Relative market share	Industry growth rate
1	Spare parts	119	100%	31	26%	0.73	+14

Low -20

Interpretation:

Our industry is in star quadrant and represent that it's have great opportunity for growing and improve the profitability and it is advantage for us to enter in the growing and profitable industry. So recommended strategies are:

- Product Development
- Market development
- Market penetration
- Backward, forward, or horizontal Integration

The IE Matrix

The IEF score 3.05
 The EFE score 3.09

The Total IFE Weighted Scores

Strong	Average	Weak
4.0 to 3.0	2.99 to 2.0	1.99 to 1.0

I. 3.0 3.0	II.	III.
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The
 EFE
 Total
 Weighted
 Scores

Medium	IV.	V.	VI.
2.0	VII.	VIII.	IX
Weak			
1.0			

Division	Sales (RS) in millions	Sales %	Profit (RS) in millions	Profit %	The IEF Scores	The EFE scores
Spare parts	119	100%	31	26%	3.05	3.09

Interpretation:

The intersection points of IFE and EFE lies in quadrant 1, which is the part of Grow and build region so, the recommended strategies are:

- Product Development
- Market development
- Market penetration
- Backward, forward, or horizontal Integration

Grand Strategy Matrix

Slow market growth

Interpretation:

The organization lays in Quadrant I so, there is a rapid market growth and strong competitive position, so and the recommended strategies are:

- Market penetration
- Market development
- Product development
- Forward & backward integration
- Diversification

The stage 3: Decision

QSPM Matrix

Key factors		Market development		Market penetration	
Opportunities	Weights	AS	TAS	AS	TAS
Change in tax	0.05	3	0.15	2	0.1
Launch of youth entrepreneur scheme	0.15	1	0.15	1	0.15
GDP trends	0.06	3	0.18	1	0.06
Population	0.27	4	1.08	4	1.08

Broadband and mobile users	0.05	1	0.04	3	0.12
Increase growth in media tools	0.04	2	0.04	2	0.04
Threats					
Labor laws	0.03	3	0.09	4	0.12
Environmental protection laws	0.05	4	0.20	3	0.09
Unemployment	0.1	3	0.24	2	0.16
Inflation	0.15	4	0.60	4	0.60
Lack of technology	0.05	2	0.06	1	0.03
Totals	1		2.83		2.55
Strengths					
High quality spare parts	0.25	4	1.0	3	0.75
Trained and experience staff	0.1	3	0.3	4	0.40
Timely New Model	0.1	3	0.3	4	0.4
Strong R & D	0.05	3	0.15	4	0.20
AI system	0.06	4	0.12	3	0.09
Weaknesses					
High cost of production	0.1	3	0.30	3	0.30
Limited geographical area	0.15	3	0.30	4	0.40
Dealership networks	0.07	3	0.30	2	0.20
Costly Spare parts	0.05	4	0.20	4	0.20
Lack of capital	0.07	3	0.21	4	0.28
Totals	1		3.18		3.22
Total scores			6.01		5.77

Interpretation:

Total attractive score of **Market Development is 6.01 and market penetration is 5.77** which suggest that market Development Strategy is suitable for our company. We should introduce their products and services to those areas where they haven't reached yet (increase the geographical area for selling products).

Strategic Formulation Analytical Framework (2) & (3)

Acceptability

If the new strategy would fulfill the expectations of the stakeholders the acceptability will occur. It's resulted from financial and non -financial aspects. It deals with the measurements of risk, returns and stakeholder expectations. As we are providing high quality accessories with features of water proof, luxury and termite proof at lowest cost, this will cause to build reputation of company among consumers.

Our aim is geographical expansion with providing parts in Karachi, Gujranwala, Abbottabad as well as across the Pakistan and those who cannot buy expensive boards will also buy as our alternative boards. For this, we will invest in marketing campaign, implement the strategies and then measure the sales and financial performance. In strategic formulation analytical framework, I our market development strategy is selected and this strategy will be definitely accepted by their customers due to whom our company can get more profit and competitive advantage in the market.

Suitability

Suitability deals with the fact that effectively and efficiently utilizes the company resources of chosen strategy after identify strengths and weakness from internal audit and opportunities and threats from external audit. Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) will help us to determine which strategy would be suitable for our company.

According to QSPM which is covered in phase 3, our selected strategy is Market Development Strategy that would be suitable for our company. Our market development strategy score is **4.56** which mean we should focus on the customers who cannot buy luxury parts because of expensive and also focus on increase the market share. We should also try to expand geographical area from Karachi to Gujranwala to all over Pakistan to obtain many customers and it will help us to grow and earn more profit.

Feasibility

Feasibility deals with the fact that how and what resources would be use to implement the chosen strategy. These resources include equipment, time, money and also people. As we are starting new business so we have resources to implement these strategies. Feasibility is further divided into seven sub categories which define whether the company has enough resources to implement the chosen strategy.

1. Machinery:

TAJ-Autos has machinery which has been purchased from China and Tiawan at lowest price to run production and it is main part of business

2. Makeup:

The infrastructure we are developed is enough and strong and there will be no need to change overall make-up of the company.

3. Management:

TAJ- Autos will be hire qualified and hire only those staff which have experience or well trained and we will be focus on management policy to be more market orientated.

4. Markets:

We need to arrange or make more resources in establishing a proper marketing team that not only understands the market demands and needs but also design marketing policies and strategies accordingly to promote and growth of our business

5. Men and Women:

We will be focus on hiring women as well as men whose are deal with customers and hire well experience marketing team whose make strong and valid policies to make business more efficient and effective.

6. Methods:

TAJ-Autos would be focusing production process with the newest technologies due to which it is highly efficient and doesn't need to be changed for the strategy implementation and it will be help us to developed new market

7. Money:

In Pakistan as well as Karachi and Gujranwala, most of the suppliers, wholesalers and retailers done business of spare parts on credit and pay after on due date therefore we have not an efficient way of handling money.

All rest part of strategic framework 2 already covered in External plan, Internal Plan.

Strategic formulation framework 3

Question: 1 what are the industry's dominant economic traits?

We are entering in the manufacturing and import from foreign countries of Auto parts (engine parts, internal and external parts of car) industry and it plays an important role in the economy of Pakistan.

Market size and growth rate:

Pakistan Motor Vehicles Sales Growth rate is updated monthly, available from Jul 2006 to Dec 2022, with an average growth rate of 5.9 %. The data reached an all-time high of 22,420.5 % in Apr 2021 and a record low of -99.6 % in Apr 2020. Car Sales of Pakistan recorded 17,196.0 units in Dec 2022. Its contribution to the national exchequer is nearly Rs. 50-billion (US\$220 million). Pakistan's auto market is among the smallest but fastest growing in Asia. 269,792 cars were sold in 2018 but declined to 186,716 in 2019 due to austerity measures.

Competitors in the industry:

There are following main competitors in manufacturing of automotive industry of Pakistan:

- Honda South Private limited
- Stand Tech Private limited
- Al-Rafey Auto Limited
- Pak Wheels Auto Parts & Accessories
- Toyota Zarghoon Motors

Entry Exit barriers:

Anyone can enter the market with having sufficient capital but there are an entry barrier is that brand loyalty and customer trust on spare parts and accessories, even if price is high. So, we have such barriers to enter in the business and create reputation among customers. The barriers to exit are very low we can exit from business at any time.

Industry profitability:

As per reports, the manufacturing of spare parts and accessories industry is quite profitable. Profit margin can be defined as the percentage of revenue that a company retains as income after the deduction of expenses. Group 1 Automotive net profit margin as of December 31, 2022 is 4.57%

Product and customer characteristics:

We are serving Pakistani auto-parts industry with our product which different parts we make that are very low in price and high in quality with having different features like water proof, plastic and termite proof. Customer can buy it from wholesaler and retailer easily.

Customer always prefer low price with quality products so those brands offer him lowest price customer will buy things from them. So, this is our major competitive advantage to attract the customer.

Prevalence of backward integration:

To achieve the competitive advantage, we are using the strategy of backward integration where we are directly link with supplier into contracts and work as manufacturer. We are producing and import the parts from different suppliers from different countries and delivered it to wholesaler/retailer.

Question: 2 What Is Competition Like and How Strong Are the Competitive Forces?

The results we got were:

- Threat of new entrants (low)
- Rivalry among competitors (moderate)
- Threat of substitute products (moderate)

- Bargaining power of suppliers (high)
- Bargaining power of buyers (high)

We have a high competitive rivalry as there are many competitors in Pakistan. All the competitors are trying to achieve the same quality that is standard in the industry. All the competitors try to be the cost leader in the industry and offer almost similar prices for the products. This causes the competition to be high as well.

Question 3: What Forces Are at Work to Change Industry conditions?

There are following many forces that may change manufacturing of auto parts industry in the upcoming years. These forces can be proving as opportunities for us or threat for us.

- To be effective and efficient in the processes, technological advantage will be an opportunity for us
- In this innovative era digitalization is increase day by day that will help us to reach new customers and untapped market.
- Regulatory prices, new tax policies, and government legislation and government policies keep changing may also cause to affect our business and it is a threat for us.
- The government-imposed GST of 18% few years which caused a massive increase in price and situation got unfavorable for the industry.
- As increase in population, consumption needs and lifestyle of peoples are changing day by day, this will help to grow the industry.

Question 4: Which companies are in the weakest/strongest position?

Strategic group maps are used to identify the strategic positions of different companies in an industry.

Group map 1

The map shows the companies grouped according to the strategic variables of price and quality. We can see that Pak wheels group has a high quality and high price products as compared to Al-Rafey, TAJ-Autos and Stand tech limited. Price of TAJ-Autos is low and quality is high as compared to others.

Group map 2

Group map 2

The map shows the companies grouped according to the strategic variables of price and quality. We can see that Pak wheels group compete at global market and sale their products globally as well as compared to Al- Rafey auto who are sale their product at globally but competing only in local market. You can also see that our company TAJ-Autos sale their products in local market and as well compete in local market at starting.

Question 5: What Strategic moves the competitors are likely to make next?

We need to analyze current strategies, strengths, weaknesses and resources to predict the future strategies of competitors. We analyze already about competitors and predict following strategies:

Increase product line:

The competitors may try to expand their product line by introducing High goods material products after analyzing our business. This will allow them to tap into new markets and attain more customers. This will increase competition in market and increase their brand reputation.

Try to find new suppliers:

There are number of suppliers in Pakistan who provides raw material to competitors. They may increase their suppliers after entering into new contracts and that will give them quality raw material and provide them competitive advantage over other competitors.

Question 6: What are the key factors for competitive success?

According to CPM conducted in phase 3, we can say that, key factors for competitive success of TAJ-Autos are:

Product quality:

We are mainly focus on brand equity that is providing the quality of the products. We are buying our quality raw materials and try to produce the best quality products at lowest prices.

Price:

We are providing high quality boards with lowest price than other parts at lowest price and this is our major competitive advantage and fastest growing business.

Advertisement:

We launch display center and make display on walls about our boards on wholesaler and retailer shop and also focusing on market strategies to promote our business.

Question 7: Is the industry attractive or unattractive?

Manufacturing of auto parts industry is one of the fastest growing industries in Pakistan. As the spare parts and accessories are used in Car and if person modifying their cars, we will provide those parts they are available in Pakistan. This industry is growing as competitive industry are grows. The industry also contributes to the country's annual GDP round about 1% to 3%. The industry is very profitable but competition in the market is tough as brand reputation and customer interest in new and different luxury and cheapest price of parts. Our porter forces results is following:

- Threat of new entrants (low)
- Rivalry among competitors (moderate)
- Threat of substitute products (moderate)
- Bargaining power of suppliers (high)
- Bargaining power of buyers (high)

The industry is not much attractive and there is perfect competition in markets as rivalry among competitors is moderate and there have a chance to new entrants in market as well for us it is a good chance to enter in market and take many competitive advantages.

Marketing Plan

Consumer Research and Marketing Strategy

SMART Marketing Objective:

- Our goal is to increase the brand awareness in area which we have targeted segment.
- Our aim is to build strong customer relationship by giving them 10% discounts on total bill payment
- Our aims is to provide those type of spare parts that are not available in Pakistan.
- Our target is to increase our sales by at least 10% in next three years.
- Our aim to increase in customers by 30% and create brand reputation in the end of three years.

Consumer Audit

Research objectives:

- Our research goal is to know how much demand in market of particle spare parts and accessories of cars owners.
- Recognize the market potential
- Attitude of people towards our product

Research Methodology:

In order to understand and analyze the demand of our product in the market we held research through questionnaire.

- This study consists of **Quantitative analysis** and the **Questionnaire** has been employed as research tool
- The respondents of this study were the wholesaler and retailers of Karachi and Gujranwala auto market that are buying and selling boards in Gujranwala. (B2B)
- The study is based on the total of **159 Questionnaires with 16 questions** because we are dealing in **B2B** so our focus was also in B2B in order to know demand of our product in the market.

Data analysis (B2B):

Interpretation:

The graph indicates that there are 95% of males and 5% of females of our questionnaire's responses. 159 people Responses.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are most number of peoples working in auto parts market is 10 th pass ratio is 55% and graduated that is almost 25.9%.

Interpretation:

The graph indicates that the business size of our respondents that shows 28.9% have small business size, 45.1% medium business and large business size is 27%. As a result, in Gujranwala most wholesaler and retailers have medium business size.

Interpretation:

The graph shows the wholesalers and retailers monthly sale 30% respondents show that their sale is 50,000 above. 11% respondents show that their sale is 1,000,000 and above.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 39% wholesalers and retailers have 2 suppliers and 35.6% have 4 or more than 4 suppliers.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 79.7% respondents who are satisfied with their suppliers.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that 20.2% respondents shows that they sale 1000 Auto-parts in one month and 15.3% say that they are selling 5000 auto parts in one month.

Interpretation: The graph shows that 20 % respondents sale batteries mostly. 55.1% sale Main Auto parts and 24.9% shows the Modifying parts

Interpretation:
The graph shows that 60% of customers demand quality products and 30% of customer bargain on price.

Are customer like to buy our stylish and new products and we give a customize service also?

Interpretation: The graph shows that 83.7% respondents says that they are buying our quality products.

11. What is type of your targeted area?

59 responses

Interpretation:

The graph shows that 67.8% respondent's sale their parts in urban area like Karachi and Gujranwala city.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 60% respondents whose complain for warranty or limited life cycle.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 39.8% respondents say that customer pay maximum of Rs 10,000 for one or both parts and 10% respondents say that customer can pay maximum of 80,000 for one or both spare parts.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 40.7% respondents who say that we are place a order both daily and weekly base but it is depend on order size.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there are 82.7% respondents who say that we are get rid of spare parts.

Interpretation:

The graph shows that there is 20% respondents whose say that customer demand for batteries mostly and 35% customer both are demand for external, internal parts or accessories of Cars.

Identification & formation of market segments

Segment 1:

Geographic segment

Country	Pakistan
Region	Sindh
City	Karachi
Urban/Rural	Urban

Area	Malir, Defense, Bahira town, Cantt
Industry	Manufacturing/Import of Auto parts

Demographic segmentation

Age	18-25 years
Gender	Male
Occupation	Students
Revenue	Rs 20,000-50,000 per month
Business size	Medium
Education	Intermediate & Graduation

Psychographic segmentation

Personality	Talkative and conscious (try new things)
Interest	Consumer interest in luxury parts
Lifestyle	Liberals (they are singles and does not have any busy routine and they have large friend circle)
Social status	Upper and middle class

Behavioral segmentation

User status	Moderate user
Usage rate	Medium
Customer loyalty	High
Preference	Quality products and Stylish Parts
Event	Modifying his cars

Segment 2:

Geographic segment

Country	Pakistan
Region	Sindh
Urban/Rural	Urban
Area	Malir, Defense, Bahira town, Cantt
Industry	Manufacturing & Import of Autos parts

Demographic segmentation

Age	25-35 years
Gender	Both
Revenue	50,000- 100,000 per month
Business size	Medium
Education	Graduation or Post-Graduate's
Family Size	Singles as well as married

Psychographic segmentation

Personality	Dominant
Interest	Consumer interest in modifying his old/new Cars
Lifestyle	Professional/Modern
Social status	High class, Upper Middle Class

Behavioral segmentation

User status	Moderate / High
Usage rate	High
Customer loyalty	High
Preference	Price & Quality of products
Event	Modifying his cars

Segment 3:

Geographic segment

Region	Sindh, Punjab
City	Karachi, Gujranwala
Urban/Rural	Urban
Area	Karachi/Gujranwala Cantt, Bahira Town, City Housing, Dc colony & Malir
Industry	Manufacturing/ Import of Auto parts

Demographic segmentation

Age	35 and above years
Gender	Both
Occupation	Businessman
Revenue	150,000 or above per month
Business size	Medium
Education	Matric, Graduation, Post Graduates

Psychographic segmentation

Personality	Busy persons and conservative personality
Interest	Consumer interest in modifying his old/new Cars
Lifestyle	Professional / Socially Active
Social status	High Class, Upper Middle class

Behavioral segmentation

User status	Regular
Usage rate	High
Customer loyalty	Medium
Preference	Price
Event	For Car repairs

Evaluation of Market Segments

Variables	Segment 1 (Defense market)	Segment 2 (Gulshan Abad)	Segment 3 (Wapda Town Market)
Measurable	5	3	3
Sustainable	3	4	3
Accessible	4	3	2
Differentiable	5	3	5
Actionable	2	5	2
Totals	19	18	14

Score:

- 1 (least important)
- 2 (somewhat important)
- 3 (Moderate important)
- 4 (very important)
- 5 (absolutely important)

Results and comments:

- **Segment 1:**

Segment 1 has highest total score and attractive market segment for TAJ – Autos.

In this segment, we have better chance to introduce our business products in the defense market phase 8 because of geographic area of Karachi.

- **Segment 2:**

Segment 2 has reasonable score and it is attractive market segment for TAJ-Autos. In

this segment, we have batter chance to launch our product in Gulshan abad sadar karachi.

- **Segment 3:**

Segment 3 has lowest score and unattractive segment for TAJ-Autos. It is a area we should not or we will focus after some time more for targeting the consumers.

The target market strategy:

Our segment definition is in and of itself strategic. We are not intending to satisfy all users of racing equipment, but rather those who are just starting out and those who are struggling to keep up. We can save our customers time and money, not so much within our pricing structure, but by

assessing their needs and directing them toward the proper product. Racers, by nature, tend to desire a high-end product, when often a low to mid-end product will do as good as, or sometimes even a better job. By always dealing in an honest and ethical manner, we will build customer loyalty and word-of-mouth sales that many of our competitors are lacking. As we are in B2B business so wholesalers and retailers will purchase imported spare parts from, in addition to that retailer can also buy from wholesaler.

Anticipated total Demand of the segment

- **Total population**

The total population of Gujranwala and Karachi is 35,014,196 according to the Pakistan bureau of statistics.

- **Urban population**

The urban citizens of Gujranwala are 2,948,936

The urban citizen of Karachi is 20,137,290

- **Total customers**

There are estimated 37% of wholesalers and 63% of retailers in Karachi and Gujranwala targeted market.

Wholesalers = **111**

Retailers = **190**

Totals = 301

- **Respondents**

Total responses= 159

There are **84.7%** respondents those are interested to buy our products according to questionnaires survey.

- **Demand**

According to our survey, there are 52.5% peoples respond that they are selling average 2,500 units per month

Demand= 2,500* 12= 30,000 units/year

Business Sales expected in 5 years

Years	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Sales	46,200,000	50,127,000	55,390,335	53,728,624	55,877,769

In 2024, we are calculating our sale by using market demand is 30,000 units/ year that will increase by 8.5% in 2025, 10.5% in 2026, 3% decrease in 2027 and then increase again in 2028 by 4%.

Brand positioning

We are going to offer our customer with quality boards at lowest price.

POPs

- Shades of all type of parts
- Size of all parts
- Some engine and external parts have unlimited life.
- Easily available from the market
- Having feature of Water proof, 5D and 7D leather

PODs

- Our plastic price is lowest than other companies' parts.
- Our luxury and import products have also cheap and best stylish parts.

- We are entering in the auto parts market with innovative product like quality head lights.

Marketing Objectives

Product strategy

- **Product objectives:**

- In order to achieve level of customer satisfaction and trust, we will be maximizing the quality and sustainability of our product
- To attract the customer, we will reduce the cost of our spare parts with appropriate price.

- **Product line:**

We are providing so many types of parts and give customize service

- Plastic parts
- Imported parts
- New Headlights
- Engine Parts

- **Characteristics of product/Parts:**

- Our parts have a warranty and its local or imported both are best.
- Internal auto parts are quality orientated
- Easily available from market at standard size.

- **Functions:**

- Our customer will meet us face to face or by phone calls for ordering the quantity of spare parts

- Quantity will be loaded at vehicle from warehouse and deliver to the wholesaler and retailer.
- Wholesalers will sale to retailer as well as directly sale to customer.

- **Features:**

- Water proof
- Imported best & new parts
- Internal accessories are 7-D, 9-D parts
- Unlimited life cycle
- Customize Service

- **Benefits:**

Below are some benefits of having car accessories:

- **Give premium look:**
- Auto accessories give your car a smart look. They give your car a premium and better look than it would without them. Accessories help make your car beautiful to match it to the exterior perfectly.
- **Supreme-Quality accessories:**
- You may not have bought a luxury car, but by installing a few luxurious accessories, you can give eye-appealing look to your car. You can change your car's dashboard to provide supreme-quality covers that last long and give a good look to your car.
- **Protect from wear and tear:**
- Some accessories also protect your vehicle from wear and tear. For example, when you buy a car seat cover, you protect your seats. High-quality car cover will not only safe-guard your car against a lot of dust,

but it will also keep the car safe from many other environmental hazards, such as bad weather and adverse sun rays.

- **Save from emergency situation:**
- Some car accessories like ropes and wheel wrenches help you get out of an emergency situation smoothly. Many such accessories are not used frequently, but when the need comes, they could be a time-saving accessory. For example, you stop on a journey, and when you turn the keys, nothing happens. Your car does not start. It happens when the car's battery is not working and requires a jump. In this case, a booster cable can help get the desired results. Hence you must have them in your car.

- **Give personalized look:**
- If you want to give your car a personalized look and make your long journey comfortable, you can achieve it easily with certain accessories. You can have a mobile holder to make your car spacious and comfortable. It provides the right place to keep your smartphone and also enables other areas to be optimally utilized for other purposes.
- **Improve performance:**
- Some accessories like rear windshield wipers, LED, and fog lights help in improving the performance of your car and must definitely be considered.

- **Packaging**

We are not dealing with packaging but we are labelling our brand sticker will be label on each board.

- **Warranty and Guarantee**

- If the wholesaler or retailer found any defect in electronic auto parts, they can exchange them in 30 working days.
- Some internal car accessories are life time warranty like Seat cover, stylish rims, Car mats e.t.c.

Pricing Strategy

- Pricing objective:

- Our aim to maximize the profit through loyalty of customer and earn profit of up to 50 million by the end of 1st year

- **Cost structure**

Cost	Amount
Plastic	Rs 270 (1kg)
Leather	Rs 770 (1 kg)
Chemicals	Rs 893 (1 mm)
Imported Parts (One container)	70,000,000
Labor cost	492,000
Production cost	42,330
Transportation cost	50,370

Utilities	103,450
Licensing cost	100,000
Rent	20,000
Salaries and wages	340,000
Repairs and maintenance	23,430
Taxes	87,620

Product Line	Units (Per month)	Avg sale price per unit	COGS per Unit	Margin Per Unit
Bumpers (Sheet)	1700	Rs. 1200.00	Rs. 750	Rs. 450.00
Seats Covers (5D)	1500	Rs. 2850.00	Rs. 2100	Rs. 750.00
Trunk Mats (5D)	1500	Rs. 2700.00	Rs. 2000	Rs. 700.00
Floor Mats (5D)	1500	Rs. 3500.00	Rs 2500	Rs 1,000.00
Sun Shades (3D)	1000	Rs. 700.00	Rs 200	Rs 500.00
Dashboards (3D-Printed)	2000	Rs. 850.00	Rs 450	Rs. 450.00

- **Pricing Strategy:**

As we are entering in the market as new company and want to gain market share our pricing strategy will be:

- **Penetration strategy:** we are new in the market and provide unique product with features of water proof, un stretch, unbreakable with high quality and our customize service of imported parts. This type of Products/Service is launching

first time in market therefore it would be taking time to be recognized and praised by consumers. Our price would be less than some external parts in the market. After people's interest and acknowledgement among our parts, we can increase our price accordingly.

- **Promotions Strategy**

- **Promotional objectives:**

- To be a brand in manufacturing of automotive industry
- Establish image and reputation in consumer's mind
- Our aim to reach maximum customers through effective marketing strategies

- **Promotions Mix:**

- **Social media marketing:** we will be reaching our customers by using social media tools as Facebook and Instagram pages. We hire outsource persons to handle these pages.
- **Website:** we will be launching a website of our business where wholesaler and retailer of boards will contact us for information or discussion.
- **Display advertising:** we will target our customers and awareness of our product by using visuals tool like banners, images and text images on website.
- **Wall display:** banners will be use on the wholesaler or retailer shops that will be contains pictures, features of parts.
- **Bill boards:** billboard banner will be used for the awareness of our brand.

- **Pamphlets:** we will be using pamphlets to advertise our company product. Pamphlets will be sending to wholesalers and retailer with order delivery.
- **Label printing:** Sticker of our company logo and slogan will be stick on each board.

- **Media cost:**

	Price	Quantity	Initial cost
Social media marketing			187,650
Advertising and printing			70,340
Flex and banners (5 by 2)	850	40	34,000
Pamphlets	5	3500	17,500
Brochures	30	500	15,000
Billboard expenses			24,340
Other expenses			34,300
Total media cost			383,300

Operational Plan

SMART Supply Chain, Production. Distribution Objectives:

- Reduce the manufacturing cost by 20% in next three years
- Make possible to fastest delivery in 2 working days by using time management system that are used in making some parts or deliver some import parts.

- Our objective is to hire efficient labor and provide them some incentives so that they will become more efficient and job satisfied it will lead to increase in productivity.

Complete Supply Chain and Logistics Design

- **Suppliers:**

- Foreign Suppliers
- Plastic supplier
- Steel supplier

- **Manufacturing process**

- Machinery
- Put plastic into machinery
- Put chemicals into machine.
- Run the machine
- Receive a plastic sheets and plastic button for stylish covers
- Lamination
- Finished the parts

- **Wholesaler:**

- Delivery of spare parts to wholesaler
- Peoples who buy spare parts from us in large quantity and put them into their warehouse

- Sale them to retailer as well as end consumer
- **Retailer:**
 - Retailer can buy spare parts from wholesaler as well as buy direct from us
 - Buy parts in limited quality and sale them to end consumer

Supply chain and logistics design

Procurement and purchasing

There are following items to be procured and purchase before starting our operations:

- **Contracts with supplier:**

We have suppliers of Brake pads China, JB Auto spare parts, Grand Auto Hut, Hanley auto lights e.tc. They are providing material to us at lowest price. We are entering into contracts with them and they are responsible to provide us parts and chemicals for plastic making parts.

- **Modifying Parts:**

Modifying parts is main material for us it is used for customer Car stylish and we are purchasing these parts from these following suppliers:

- JB Auto Parts China
- Grand Auto Huts

- **Plastic/Chemical Supplier**

Plastic dana we are taking from in Karachi for making a back sheet of bumpers of car and we are also purchasing this chemical from following suppliers:

- Faheem Plastic Limited
- Vertex chemicals pvt ltd

- **Production line:**

We are purchasing complete machinery that includes making, cutting and laminating that are used to make a plastic part from China at possible lowest price.

- **Furniture and fixtures:**

We are purchasing furniture that includes tables, chairs and sofas from local market and also purchase AC, Stationary etc. from local market to run daily operations.

Supplier Evaluation and Policies

There are following several factors that are to be considered while evaluating the suppliers:

- **Quality:**

For TAJ-Autos, quality is an important measurement. The raw materials such as Plastic and chemical and others are required in high quality that will make our best plastic parts for Cars. We are entered in contracts with our raw materials suppliers and price will be set.

- **Productivity:**

As we discussed, our imported parts and plastic parts are having high quality, This will show that our production is efficient. Suppliers play a vital role in production. They provide us high quality raw material at lowest price.

- **Risk capacity:**

Startup businesses remain in risk until inception therefore; suppliers play a vital role to reduce this risk throughout best supply chain.

- **Contracts:**

We are entered in contracts with suppliers on the basis of defined terms and conditions that includes price of raw material, quantity, and quality material.

For Pakistani Supplier's policies:

- Suppliers must follow the terms and conditions that are defined under contract
- Suppliers should be registered in Pakistan
- Suppliers should be avoided any type of corruption.
- Human rights should be properly followed by suppliers

For Foreign Supplier's policies:

- Suppliers must follow the terms and conditions that are defined under contract.
- Supplier should be registered in his country.
- Supplier should be avoided any type of corruption.

Operational Process

- **Production:**

All the activities are performed under production line to make a plastic making parts for car. These activities include raw materials putting, processing, cutting, sizing etc.

- **Warehousing:**

When products are ready, we are stored them into warehouse as stock. Likewise, when finished products are ready, we stored them into ware house immediately. This process also called inventory.

- **Order receiving and placement:**

The wholesaler will order by phone call as well as they can meet us face to face for order. All orders will be placed into 2 working days. Customers will register themselves in our company and they fill a detailed form that include how much quantity are needed to them and in which time they made payments.

- **Delivery of order:**

After receiving order and placed them, our delivery boy loaded quantity into vehicle and deliver it into location of our customer, our sales person also go with driver and unloaded their quantity and receive the payments physically if they wanted to pay it, otherwise cheque payments will be made.

Production Plan

Manufacturing Process:

A kind of bumper injection molding process, comprises the steps:

The first step: selecting properly injection machine, the performance of injection machine directly affects the quality of molding goods, and the injection machine of different size and performance requirement need be selected bolt special, selects to bring into the mould of losing core when the injection molding of this bumper.

Second step: raw material is selected and pretreatment, bumper Shooting Technique raw material is selected polypropylene, utilize baking oven to be dried polypropylene, baking temperature is 80 degrees Celsius to 90 degrees Celsius, and screw in injection molding machine and hot flow path are heated to 200 degrees Celsius, polyethylene is joined in injection machine barrel, be heated to happy and harmonious state.

The 3rd step: injection stage, the polypropylene of molten condition is expelled in the cavity body of mould after heating through heat treated hot-runner nozzle, injection temperature is the key factor that affects injection pressure, and bumper injection molding process injection stage of the present invention has 4 bringing-up sections, and there is its suitable processing temperature in each stage, injection temperature must be controlled in certain scope, temperature can not be too low, the low quality that can affect profiled member of temperature, and temperature is too high, can make raw material decompose, cause waste.

A kind of optimal technical scheme, be divided into four little stage steps at injection stage, sprue place is the first stage, runner to cast gate place is second stage, product is full of die cavity approximately 95% for the phase III, remainder is fourth stage section, first stage injection pressure is 80,000 grams/cm, second stage injection pressure is 90,000 grams/cm, phase III injection pressure is double centner/square centimeter, fourth stage pressure is 50,000 grams/cm, and the cast gate of described bumper injection molding process injection stage is chosen as spot pouring mouth.

The 4th step: mould closure, makes solid plate and moving platen closure.

The 5th step: pressurize, in pressure maintaining period, the nozzle of injection machine is constantly to die cavity feed supplement, dwell time setting is set according to product thickness, as long as product surface is without significant depressions, the effect of packing stage is continue to press, compacting melt, increase plastic density, in the later stage of pressurize, density of material continues to increase, plastic is moulding gradually also, till packing stage will be continued until that cast gate solidifies sealing, described bumper injection molding process dwell pressure is 85% left and right of filling maximum pressure, keeping pressure is 60 kilograms every cubic centimeter, the packing pressure time is 5 to 10 seconds.

The 6th step: in the locked mode stage, in pressure upper zone, plastics are comparatively closely knit, and density is higher, and in pressure lower region, plastics are comparatively loose, and density is lower, therefore causes Density Distribution to change with location and time. Pressure in die cavity is passed to die wall surface by plastics, has the trend that struts mould, therefore needs suitable clamp force to carry out locked mode. The mould power that rises can slightly strut mould under normal conditions, has help for the exhaust of mould; If but the mould power that rises is excessive, easily causes products formed burr, flash, even struts mould,

A kind of optimal technical scheme, the described locked mode stage selects to have enough injection machines of large clamp force, to prevent the mould phenomenon that rises.

The 7th step: cooling, make to be cooled with circulating water, in the time producing automobile bumper injection mould tool, selection can be carried out the die heater of accurately controlling, and must set cool time according to product thickness, mold temperature, material property etc.

Because molded plastic products only have cooling curing to arrive certain rigidity, after the demolding, just can avoid plastic products to produce distortion because being subject to external force, owing to accounting for whole molding cycle approximately 70%~80% cool

time, therefore design significantly shortening forming time of good cooling system, improve injection moulding productivity ratio, reduce costs.

Described cooling stage adopts cooling water pipe configuration mode. Cooling water pipe is the closer to die cavity, and caliber is larger, and number is more, and cooling effect is better, and cool time is shorter.

A kind of optimal technical scheme, coolant adopts beryllium copper, as far as possible logical cooling water in beryllium copper.

The 8th step: ejection phase, the demolding is the important link in automobile bumper injection mould tool moulding circulation, will ensure that goods are stressed evenly when the demolding, causes the defects such as deformation of products while preventing from ejecting.

A kind of optimal way, bumper injection molding process adopts push rod stripping means, to ensure product quality. The setting of push rod should be tried one's best evenly, and position should be selected in the place of ejection resistance maximum and bumper plastic strength and stiffness maximum, in order to avoid plastic deformed damaged.

The 9th step: surface treatment, the decorative pattern of product surface is processed, the polishing position that product surface requires, dark muscle position, polishing, blasting treatment are carried out in the place that product stripping has some setbacks.

The invention has the beneficial effects as follows: bumper adopts as above technique can improve production of articles efficiency, reduce product production cost, improves the quality of finished product.

Physical Plant

Machinery and Equipment

- Dust separator
- Hydraulic Hot press

- Seasoning Chamber
- Computers
- Vehicle
- Printers
- Stationary
- AC
- LED

Location and Physical facility layout

Location of our manufacturing company is in Karachi Industrial Area that is located at Korangi area.

Physical facility layout

<u>Office 2</u> Marketing	<u>Office 1</u>	<u>Office 3</u> Operation manager
<u>Office 4</u> Accounting and finance manager		Washroom
<u>Office 5</u> administrative		
<u>Office 6</u> Manufacturing In charge		Meeting room

Demographics of location vs. target markets

Our location will be industrial area Korangi area in Karachi that is located at Defense 7 and it is our demographical area. Big Showroom and warehouse of auto parts will be located in Karachi and Gujranwala and Abbottabad. In future, we are entering with them in contracts as well and they are liable to provide us quality plastic dana.

Our target market area is Karachi, Gujranwala and Lahore. In future, we will expand our geographical area and deliver our products in all over Pakistan.

Leasing, Renting, Ownership

TAJ-Autos will be renting a building for production line and office working of 2 Canal in Karachi industrial area.

TAJ-Autos will be renting a building of 10 Marla for warehousing and store all into the building.

The detail of prices and rent will be discussed in financial plan

Labor needs and supply

Position	Number of peoples
Labor for manufacturing	12
Sales man	2
peon	1
Security gauds	1
Warehouse supervisor	1
Manufacturing In charge	1
Total labor	17

Wage rates

- Rs 25 per unit is given to every labor who are working in production line
- 0.5% of sales are wage of sale man

Environmental concerns

- We are using Plastic which contains plastic material therefore, it is environmental concern for us
- We are using chemicals as furnish for thickness of plastic. After completing the process, there will be wasted resin and it is water pollution and we will be avoided to waste in water.
- We should try to focuses on ensuring minimum environmental waste

Physical facility size requirement

Our office size will be 4.5 Marla as we are discussed above in physical plant. There are following requirements:

- Computers
- Printer
- Chairs
- Tables
- Vehicle
- One piece of all parts
- Sofas
- Printer
- Stationary
- Fax installation
- AC
- LED
- CCTV cameras

Worker disability law compliance

In order to provide employment, support and welfare to disabled person, government of Pakistan has passed a law for government job as well as industrial job.

- No institution whether public or private are allowed to discriminate disabled persons and violates their rights
- The government of Pakistan ensure that the disable person is equally treated like perfect person
- Incentives and other compensation will be given to disable persons.

Layout plan with dimensions

Dimensions

- **Warehousing**

We will be renting warehouse to store goods, which will be under control of our warehouse supervisor. Location of our warehouse will be Defense phase 8 Karachi and Khayali By pass Gujranwala industrial area.

Transportation

The buyer will pay all the delivery cost which includes petrol and delivery cost will depend on length of location.

- **Customer service policies**

- Buyer must confirm the quantity of parts they needed
- If parts is defected a little bit, buyer must inform us in 3 working days or return us.
- If buyer purchase goods on credit, buyer is liable to pay all their due within 1 week.

- **Inventory control**

Our warehouse supervisor will responsible to control inventory. The responsibilities are following:

- Incoming stock placement, monitor out coming stock and provide stock report to Sales manager on weekly basis

- **Policies of quality**

- We should maintain all standards of quality
- If customer find any defect in spare parts, they can exchange them within two working days.

Human Resources Plan

SMART Human Resources Objectives:

- Our aim is to hire more effective and efficient peoples for right job to increase the productivity level to 20%.
- our aim is to maintain good and longtime relationship with workforce and labor
- our aim is to create required vacancy and find a person according to the requirement of job
- Our aim to examining labor performance on 3 months basis and provide them appraisal and wages of 2% of unit so we can motivate them.
- Our aim is to decrease the rate of termination of employee and also limit employee turnover by 18%.

Organizational chart

Employee Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment and selection process for TAJ-Autos is following:

Identification of vacancy: First step is that HR manager looks for place to be filled. If there is requirement for a specific place to carry out the task HR manager identify the requirements of person that is needed for specific place. A job vacancy will also identify by HR manager after identification of requirements and moved in further steps to evaluate and choose right candidate for that specific job.

Job analysis: Job description and specifications will be defined as well as requirements of candidate will also analyze for right job.

Screening the applications: In this step, criteria of selection would be defined and screening the received applications on the basis of defined criteria. Those candidates are matched with criteria will be moved further processes and rest applications will be removed.

Interviewing: Interviewing is most important step to hire an employee or labor. Our HR manager will conduct physical interview with formal structure and selected candidate on the basis of interview and moved him for further process.

Selection and Appointment: On the basis of interview, selected candidate is hire on the specific job. Selected candidate become TAJ-Autos and processes and procedures will be discussed to him.

Training and development: New candidate will be moved further to training and learn the process and methods to behave and learn about their task in the company.

After the training, employees are showing the performance and evaluation process would be conducted on the basis of performance over certain time period which ensures that we will successfully find “right people for right job”.

Job descriptions

Job Description of CEO

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
Job Title	CEO (Chief executive officer)
Reported to	

Job brief

Board of director is hiring a CEO at TAJ-Autos. CEO is responsible for the successful leadership and management of company's business and supervises all company's operations and peoples in order to maintain and grow business.

Responsibilities

- CEO is responsible to develop and execute the company business strategies in order to achieve goals of company
- CEO is responsible to provide strategic advice to the board of director
- CEO is responsible to prepare and implement comprehensive business plans
- CEO is responsible to develop company policies and legal guidelines
- Supervise the work of HR manager, operation manager, Marketing manager and finance manager
- CEO is responsible for decision making in order to increase the growth of business

Requirements and skills

- Previous working experience as CEO for 5 years
- Master degree in business administration or similar relevant field
- Communication, presentation and leadership skills
- Growth mindset and time management skills

Job description of operational manager

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
Job Title	Operation manager
Reported to	CEO

Job brief

At TAJ-Autos, we are looking for a qualified operational manager to join us and increase productivity of the firm and handle overall company operations.

Responsibilities

- To make sure that all operations that are held at TAJ-Autos will be cost effective and appropriate
- Operation manager is responsible to purchase raw material, planning for inventory and oversee warehouse system
- Prepare the operational and strategic objectives.
- To manage the budget of operations and perform yearly production forecasting
- To monitor and control quality standards and make decision to improve quality
- Supervise the manufacturing In charge and warehouse In charge
- To improve the company operational system and processes in support of achieving organization operational objectives

Requirements and skills

- Leadership skills
- Having experience in budgeting and forecasting
- Having high skills of communication
- Master degree or degree in operational management related field with experience of 10 years about related field

Job Description of Marketing Manager

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
Job Title	Marketing manager

Reported to	CEO
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Job brief

At TAJ-Autos, we are looking for a qualified marketing manager to join us in providing their skills and experience to promote our company and set as brand in customer mind.

Responsibilities

- Marketing manager is responsible for managing all marketing activities and staff of marketing department, advertising and promotional activities
- Marketing manager is responsible for determining the demand and supply for product that offered by a TAJ-Autos
- Identification of its competitors and potential customers
- Marketing manager is responsible for develop pricing strategies with the goal of maximizing the firm's income or Market share while ensuring that our customers are satisfied with our product
- Focus on social media advertising and make effective advertising to attract the customers

Requirements and skills

- Master degree or equivalent; five to ten years related experience
- Marketing manager should have ability to calculate the demand of our product
- Marketing manager should have effective communications skill

Job Description of Accountant

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
Job Title	Accountant

Reported to	CEO
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Job brief

At TAJ-Autos, we are looking for a qualified accountant to join us in providing their financial efforts to make our company more effective and efficient.

Responsibilities

- The responsibility of accountant is to provide quarterly financial reports and interpret financial information to managerial staff for decision making
- The responsibility of accountant is to maintain Financial position and performance of company
- Focus on all daily and monthly transactions that are transact by company.
- Manage an implement the company yearly budget
- The responsibility of accountant is to analyze costs, pricing, sales results and the company actual performance.

Requirements and skills

- BS/MA degree in Finance and Accounting
- Professional certifications such as CFA or CPA or similar will be considered as plus point
- MS excel using skills
- Account related Software using skills

Job description of Administrative

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
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Job Title	Administrative
Reported to	CEO

Job brief

At TAJ-Autos, we are looking for a qualified Administrative to join us in providing their experience with us by handling hiring process, organizational systems and monitor HR strategies.

Responsibilities

- Administrative is responsible to establish and implement HR strategies
- Administrative is responsible to manage the recruitment and selection process of employees and labor at TAJ-Autos company
- Administrative is responsible to establish and monitor overall HR strategies, attendance system of employees and labor of the organization
- Administrative is responsible to create positive working environment in company
- Administrative is responsible to and manage a performance appraisal that led job satisfaction of employees and labor
- Administrative is responsible to handle salaries plan and benefits plan

Requirements and skills

- Administrative should have excellent verbal and written communication skills
- Decision making skills would be required to HR manager
- Software using skills that are related to HR
- Master degree in business administration or HR related field with 7 to 10 years' experience.

Job Description of warehouse In charge

Company Name	TAJ-Autos
Job Title	Warehouse Incharge
Reported to	Operation manager

Job brief

At TAJ-Autos, we are looking for a experience warehouse Incharge to join us in providing their experience with us by handling all warehouse system including stock in, stock out, record of stock etc.

Responsibilities

- Warehouse Incharge is responsible for monitoring How much stock coming in warehouse
- Warehouse Incharge is responsible for monitoring work in progress and finished products
- Warehouse Incharge is responsible for purchasing raw materials and store them in warehouse
- Recording all stock data into computer software
- Handle delivery matters

Requirements and skills

- BS degree in business or experience of 3 to 5 years in related field
- Communication skills
- Software using skills

Compensation and benefits

The employees will be paid a basic salary as per their relevant salary grades. In addition, they will also receive various allowances and benefits as per their performance as time to time.

- **Salary structure**

The minimum salary is set by government is Rs 25,000 to Rs, 30,000 and employs in the company will get paid on the basis of their relevant experience and subject to the skills and performance.

Holidays and leaves

There will be holidays of Eid or other Islamic religious holidays as per Islamic calendar. Leave will be allowed in case of health issues or any other personal problem with solid reason and permission would be taken from HR manager.

- **Annual Reward**

Employees' salaries will be reduce by 7% of its basic pay every year on the basis of performance and feedback from CEO.

- **Medical facility:**

Employees and their families will get free or discounted medical services from government hospital with the help of social security of employees.

HR policies

- Leave from company would be allowed and accepted with the prior permission of HR manager
- There will be meeting arranged by CEO of company in every two months to discuss the performance of company
- Employees can meet anytime with HR manager or supervisor if they have any problem to avoid any inconvenience
- There will be no any discrimination will be based upon skills
- Employees would not be allowed to go outside from company even break time
- Employees would not be allowed to using mobile phone during working hours

- Employees, who will be resigning from job, will be responsible to notice us by giving at least one month ago from resignation.
- The termination of the employees would be made due to any unethical action in the company and it would be written termination.
- The pay will be increased 7% annually on the basis of performance and feedback from CEO

Performance Appraisal

Employee Name:

Date:

Department:

Period of Review:

Reviewers Title:

Evaluation	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Comment
Job Knowledge					
Productivity					
Work Quality					
Technical Skills					
Work Consistency					
Cooperation					
Attitude					
Work Relations					
Creativity					
Punctuality					
Attendance					
Dependability					
Communication Skills					
Job Performed					
Remarks from Customers					
Overall Rating					

Rating 4= very unsatisfied 3= unsatisfied 2= satisfied 1= very satisfied

Feedback:

CEO signature _____ **Administrative Signature** _____

HOD signature _____

Legal Requirements

Relevant certifications and legal licenses

- Registration of business under partnership act 1932
- Pakistan standard and quality control authority
- Certificate of incorporation issued by SECP
- Registration of Income, Sales, and Professional Taxes with Federal board of revenue (FBR) and receive NTN.
- Registration of employees in Sindh Employee social security institution that provides safety rights and benefits to employees.

Financial Analysis

SMART financial Objectives

- Increase in sales by 11.5% in next 3 years
- Our aim is to decrease in variable cost within three years to minimize production cost in three years
- Purchase all equipment's and assets on 100% Cash- No payables
- Our aim is to minimize the expenses by 7% and utilize 60% profit of the company for further growth and improvement in next three years.

Funds required and their uses and Capital Structure

Funds component	Amount (RS)
Machinery and equipment	6,163,780
Advance rent security	227,000
Computers and printers	103,500
Telephones/fax	13,720
Office tables	41,000
office chairs	79,000
Sofas (visitor)	31,000
AC	137,000
CCTV + LCD	128,340
Fans and lightning	69,330
Broad band	5,354
Solar system	530,000
stationary	18,920
Dispenser	16,000
Interior work	93,000
License fees	100,000
Purchases (raw material)	2,780,220
opening salaries	630,000
Advertisement	220,000
Website	12,000
Cash in hand	600,836
Total funds	12,000,000

Sources of funds

Investors	Equity	Investment
Mr. Tatheer Ahmed	16.66%	2000,000
Mr. Yahya Siddique	16.66%	2000,000
Mr. Ahmed Shahzad	16.66%	2000,000
Mr. Abdullah Javed	16.66%	2000,000
Mr. Gulfam Ahmed	16.66%	2000,000
Mr. Abubakar	16.66%	2000,000
Total equity	100%	12,000,000

Sources of funds over next three years

Sources of funds of TAJ-Autos over next three years are totally equity based. We are investing our yearly income till inception of business. If we required more money, we acquired funds from others in form of loan.

Break Even Analysis

Breakeven	Total fixed cost/contribution margin		
	2024	2025	2026
Total Fixed Cost	13,108,325	13,162,688	13,260,923
Selling Price	4740	5215	5740
Variable Manufacturing Cost	2370.30	2607.1	2867.7
Contribution Margin	2369.70	2607.90	2872.30
C.M %	200%	200%	200%
Breakeven in Units	5532	5047	4617
Breakeven in sales	26,219,969	26,321,338	26,500,609

Payback period

Years	Cash Flow	Cumulative Cash Flow
2023	-12,000,000	-12,000,000
2024	2,122,464	-14,122,464
2025	15,827,321	1,704,857
2026	17,611,703	

Payback period = 1 years+ 14,122,464 / 15,827,321

Payback Period = 1 + 0.89

Payback period = 1.89 years

Discounted payback period

years	Cash flow	Discount factor @ 12%	Discounted CF	Cumulative CF
2023	-12,000,000		-12,000,000	-12,000,000
2024	2,122,464	$(1+0.12)^1 = 1.12$	1895057	-10,104,943
2025	15,827,321	$(1+0.12)^2 = 1.254$	12621468	2,516,525
2026	17,611,703	$(1+0.12)^3 = 1.405$	12535020	

Discounted Payback period = 1 years+ 10,104,943/ 12,621,468

Discounted Payback Period = 1 + 0.801

Discounted Payback period = 1.801 years

Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

years	Cash flow
2023	-12,000,000
2024	2,122,464
2025	15,827,321
2026	17,611,703
IRR	59%

Interpretation:

IRR > WACC (Accepted)

IRR < WACC (Rejected)

In this case, ($59 > 12\%$) IRR is greater than WACC so we will accept and invested in this business.

Modified Internal Rate of return (MIRR)

		FV of cash flows	
Years		Cash flows	FV= PV (1+r) ⁿ
2023		-12,000,000	
2024		2,122,464	2,662,419
2025		15,827,321	17,726,599
2026		17,611,703	17,611,703
Terminal Value			38,000,721
PV of costs			12,000,000

$$\text{MIRR} = (\text{Terminal Value} / \text{PV of cost})^{1/n} - 1$$

$$= (38,000,721 / 12,000,000)^{1/3} - 1$$

$$= (3.166)^{0.333} - 1 = 1.467 - 1 = 0.467$$

$$\text{MIRR} = 0.467 = 46.7\%$$

Interpretation:

MIRR > WACC (Accepted)

MIRR < WACC (Rejected)

In this case, ($46.7\% > 12\%$) MIRR is greater than WACC so we will accept and invested in this business.

Net present value (NPV)

Years		Cash Flow
2023		-12,000,000
2024		1895057
2025		12621468
2026		12535020
PV of Cash flows		27,051,545
Initial Cost		12,000,000

$$\text{NPV} = \text{PV of cash flows} - \text{initial cost}$$

$$= 27,051,545 - 12,000,000$$

$$\text{NPV} = 15,051,545$$

Profitability Index

Years	Cash Flows
2023	-12,000,000
2024	1895057
2025	12621468
2026	12535020
PV of Cash flows	27,051,545
Initial Cost	12,000,000

$$\text{Profitability Index} = \text{PV of cash flows} / \text{Initial cost}$$

$$= 27,051,545 / 12,000,000$$

$$\text{Profitability Index} = 2.25$$

Interpretation:

PI > 1 (Accepted)

PI < 1 (Rejected)

In this case, (2.25 > 1) PI is greater than 1 so we will accept and invested in this business.

Financial statements for first 3 years (Projected)

Projected statement of Profit and Loss			
	2023	2024	2025
Sales	46,200,000	50,127,000	55,390,335
Cost of goods sold	32,350,220	35,703,765	40,660,450
Gross profit	13,849,780	14,423,235	14,729,885
Operating expenses			
Payroll	6,833,000	6,920,000	6,790,000
Rent expense	2,760,000	3,036,000	3,339,600
Utility bills	1,953,457	1,786,233	1,912,863
Advertisement expenses	450,000	310,000	100,000
Repairs and maintenance	0	40,120	40,120
Transportation expense	240,110	199,200	210,000
Office expenses(stationary)	41,245	34,255	33,775
Telephone expense	20,000	21,000	20,500
Other administration expense	30,340	35,680	33,865
Depreciation expenses	680,694	680,694	680,694

Total operating expenses	13,008,846	13,063,182	13,161,417
Earnings before tax	840,934	1,360,053	1,568,468
Taxation-net	335,890	464,780	569,230
Net income	505,044	895,273	999,238

Projected Statement of Financial Position			
	2023	2024	2025
Assets			
Current Assets			
Cash	1,363,265	2,344,760	2,354,200
Account receivable	0	230,400	210,900
Warehouse stock inventory	2,015,000	2,233,400	2,110,300
Raw material inventory	2,780,000	3,000,400	3,240,560
Prepaid expenses	344,000	310,000	290,455
Total current Assets	6,502,265	8,118,960	8,206,415
Fixed assets			
Machinery and equipment	6,163,780	6,163,780	6,163,780
Furniture and fixtures	643,163	701,233	690,000
Accumulated Depreciation	-680,694	-1,361,388	-2,042,082
Total fixed assets	6,126,249	5,503,625	4,811,698
Total Assets	12,628,514	13,622,585	13,018,113
Liabilities and owner equity			
Current liabilities			
Account Payable	467,900	430,800	410,000
Owner equity			
Equity	12,000,000	12,000,000	12,000,000
Retained earnings	160,614	1,191,785	608,113
Total liabilities and owner equity	12,628,514	13,622,585	13,018,113

Projected statement of Cash flow			
	2023	2024	2025
Cash flow from operating activities			
operating income	840,934	1,360,053	1,568,468
depreciation expense	680,694	680,694	680,694
Tax		-335,890	-464,780
Net CF By operating activities	1,521,628	1,704,857	1,784,382
Cash flow from investing activities			
Purchases of assets	-11,399,164		
Cash flow from Financing activities			
Equity	12,000,000	12,000,000	12,000,000
Opening cash	0	2,122,464	3,827,321
Net change in cash	2,122,464	15,827,321	17,611,703

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

TAJ-Autos operations management will be effective today. It is associated with the company's particular interest in improving operational efficiency. As a result, all the techniques implemented are effective and beneficial to TAJ-Autos. However, it should be noted that their effectiveness depends on thorough and detailed planning. Overall, despite some shortcomings and weaknesses, the company remains strong and can even become more influential if its threats are transformed into opportunities. This move will make TAJ-Autos more competitive and help restore its leading position in the National auto market. Planning is another key factor in the success of TAJ-Autos. This is because the company is strongly affected by changes in the global economic environment, whether positive or negative. The basis of planning is an estimate of potential production and demand as well as major market fluctuations. On this basis, all planning activities are carried out. Thus, capacity and location planning are tied to expected changes in demand. As for the planning, it is associated with internal planning and human resource allocation. The main feature is the development of online schedules that are accessible to all employees.

Recommendation

In addition to being an influential company, there are still gaps to fill. This can be achieved by following some of these recommendations:

Focus more on innovation. For example, replacing zinc phosphate with a thin film pre-treatment system when painting to reduce the amount of natural gas in vehicle manufacturing and make the process more environmentally friendly;

Working on the balanced scorecard design, this tag is omitted. It must incorporate factors such as learning and growth, customers, financial performance, and internal business processes. It is necessary to analyze the efficiency of the business, thereby finding ways to improve operational efficiency;

- Focus on ISO 14000 certifications due to increasing popularity of green management;
- Continue to collect customer feedback to improve customer satisfaction and collect data on the most severe defects of manufactured cars (e.g. create a multilingual website);
- Introduction to the principles of lean management, recalling the successful experience of the NUMMI factory.
- Applying Goldratt's critical chain to improving project management: emphasis on building cross-cultural teams.
- Introduction of web-based systems for sharing information and knowledge.

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